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Quantifying Formulaic Flexibility of Middle High German Legal Texts

Master's Thesis

to achieve the university degree of

MA/Master of Arts

Master's degree programme: Digital Humanities

submitted to

University of Graz

Supervisor

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Centre for Information Modelling
Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities

Graz, April 2023

Abstract

This master's thesis examines formulaic language patterns in Middle High German legal texts ('charters'), using an interdisciplinary approach with diplomatic, linguistic, and computational perspectives. A charter corpus of over 7,000 documents from Monasterium.net is analyzed, and the degree of formulaicity is measured through lexical diversity indices, compression rates, and n -gram coverage, using the Reference Corpus for Middle High German as a comparison. Various techniques extract formulas, partly to determine adherence to specific charter segments, while skip probabilities and string similarity measures capture formulaic flexibility. Additionally, two fine-tuned large language models predict and quantify formula and charter slots.

Results surprisingly show only an average degree of formulaicity in charters, with a mild decrease over the 14th century. The analysis of different formula generators reveals their strengths and weaknesses, emphasizing the need for their combination in research. While skip probabilities effectively quantify formulaic preferences, they have limitations in accounting for linguistic relations beyond a formula's environment. String similarity measures are hypothesized to address this issue, quantifying formula variance not limited to predetermined structures. In addition, sequence predictions exhibit promising performance in filling formula slots and text imputation, necessitating further research.

Findings suggest the need for joining multiple techniques for a more comprehensive understanding of formulaic language patterns in Middle High German legal texts. As an outlook, the thesis highlights the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in studying historical language and the potential of computational techniques in providing insights into formulaicity and formulaic flexibility.

Kurzfassung

Diese Master-Arbeit untersucht formelhafte Sprachmuster in mittelhochdeutschen Rechtstexten ('Urkunden') unter Verwendung eines interdisziplinären Ansatzes, der diplomatische, linguistische und informationstechnische Perspektiven kombiniert. Ein Korpus von über 7.000 Urkunden aus Monasterium.net wird analysiert und der Grad der Formelhaftigkeit mittels lexikalischer Diversitätsindizes, Kompressionsraten und N-Gramm-Abdeckung gemessen, wobei das Referenzkorpus für Mittelhochdeutsch als Vergleich herangezogen wird. Danach werden Formeln mit verschiedenen Techniken extrahiert, teils um ihre Präferenz für spezifische Urkundenabschnitte zu bestimmen, während Skip-Wahrscheinlichkeiten und String-Ähnlichkeitsmaße die formelhafte Flexibilität erfassen. Zudem werden zwei auf Urkundensprache fein abgestimmte große Sprachmodelle eingesetzt, um Formel- und Urkundenteile vorherzusagen und zu quantifizieren.

Die Ergebnisse zeigen überraschenderweise nur einen durchschnittlichen Grad an Formelhaftigkeit in Urkunden, mit einem leichten Rückgang im Verlauf des 14. Jahrhunderts. Die Analyse verschiedener Formelgeneratoren offenbart deren Stärken und Schwächen und betont die Notwendigkeit, sie in der Forschung zu kombinieren. Skip-Wahrscheinlichkeiten quantifizieren zwar effektiv formelhafte Präferenzen, weisen jedoch Limitationen in der Erfassung linguistischer Beziehungen jenseits der Formelumgebung auf. String-Ähnlichkeitsmaße sollen dieses Problem angehen und formelhafte Varianz ohne vorgegebene Strukturen quantifizieren. Zudem zeigen Sequenzvorhersagen vielversprechende Ergebnisse beim Ausfüllen von Formelteilen und Textimputation, was weitere Forschung erfordert.

Die Erkenntnisse legen nahe, dass mehrere Techniken kombiniert werden müssen, um ein umfassenderes Verständnis formelhafter Sprachmuster in mittelhochdeutschen Rechtstexten zu erreichen. Die Arbeit betont die Bedeutung interdisziplinärer Zusammenarbeit bei der Untersuchung historischer Sprache und das Potenzial von computergestützten Verfahren zur Erkenntnisgewinnung zu Formelhaftigkeit und formelhafter Flexibilität.

Acknowledgements

While it took a village to raise this child, I especially thank

- the Digital Diplomatics community (#DigDipl2022), specifically Oliver Schallert for his ideas and references on analyzing historical language patterns.
- the Computational Humanities Research community (#CHR2022), specifically Lauren Fonteyn for her input on cognitive aspects of formula processing as well as Rik Hoekstra and Marijn Koolen for showing ways of quantifying formulaicity.
- Luise Borek, for giving feedback on initial ideas and drafts.
- Daniel Luger, for lending his expert opinion on diplomatic matters.
- Tamás Kovács, for sharing tips and techniques on language modelling.
- Angelos Nicolaou, for hinting at grasping formulaicity as compression.
- Fabian Theurl and Mario Walder, for doing proofs and L^AT_EX-magic.
- Georg Vogeler, Walter Scholger, and my colleagues at ZIM Graz, for making this work possible by providing an environment for the mind and spirit to blossom.
- my cats for reminding me of what it means to be human.
- my friends for telling me that I exist outside of this document.
- my family for making me try even harder.
- my partner and best friend, Janine.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASnA	Atlas spätmittelalterlicher Schreibsprachen des niederdeutschen Altlandes und angrenzender Gebiete
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
CAO	Corpus altdeutscher Originalurkunden
CEI	Charters Encoding Initiative
CEMA	Cartae Europae Medii Aevi
CRF	Conditional Random Field
CV	Computer Vision
DEEDS	Documents of Early England Data Set
DH	Digital Humanities
DiDip	From Digital to Distant Diplomatics
DL	Deep Learning
EDA	Exploratory Data Analysis
FL	Formulaic Language
HDD	Hypergeometric Distribution Diversity
HSS	Historischer Südwestdeutscher Sprachatlas
HTR	Handwritten Text Recognition
IQR	Interquartile Range
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LD	Lexical Diversity
LM	Language Model
LLR	Log-Likelihood Ratio
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MATTR	Moving Average Type-Token Ratio
MDA	Multi-Dimensional Analysis
MHG	Middle High German
MHGCDB	Middle High German Conceptual Database
MHGTA	Mittelhochdeutsches Textarchiv
MI	Mutual Information
ML	Machine Learning
MLM	Masked Language Model
MTLD	Measure of Textual Lexical Diversity
NER	Named-Entity Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OCR	Optical Character Recognition
POS	Part of Speech
ReM	Reference Corpus of Middle High German
RegEx	Regular Expression
RTTR	Root Type-Token Ratio

SFL	Systemic Functional Linguistics
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
TTR	Type-Token Ratio
VID	Vocabulaire international de la diplomatie
WMU	Wörterbuch der mittelhochdeutschen Urkundensprache
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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Part I.

Introduction and Theory

1. Introduction

This thesis analyzes formulaicity of historical legal texts in a multi-disciplinary and quantitative manner. More specifically, its flexibility is investigated. My analysis presupposes that, especially in the examined texts, there exists a phenomenon which can be regarded as formulaicity. This assumption is based on insights accumulated in the scientific disciplines of diplomatics and linguistics — both key to understanding given Formulaic Language (FL) patterns.

Formulaicity is understood here as a perceived peculiarity mainly due to a high recurrence of language segments. This is etymologically grounded: While Latin *forma* meant form or contour, its diminutive *formula* designated a more planned appearance; a register, a document, and a specific version at that [1, p. 233], [2].¹ These traces are clearly present in today's (diplomatic and linguistic) comprehension of formulaicity, i.e., a referent to features of expressions that are customary and conventionalized.

The texts under scrutiny are written in Middle High German (MHG).² Their media are documents that arguably embody the most important source for researching medieval history: charters (also deeds or diplomas).³ These are documents about acts of legal nature, issued and authenticated in accordance to certain formal requirements.⁴ They are used to conclude (and testify) transactions of or agreements about land, property, privileges, or legal rights between two or more parties [8, p. 142], [9, pp. 63, 70]. The field

¹*Formula* both as word and concept became standard repertoire in European legal contexts by the end of the 16th century, meaning a fixed and repetitive phrase. Only in the 18th century did the term gain traction in the natural sciences as equation, finally arriving at possibly being a series of signs [2].

²When defining periods for and differences between (historical) language varieties, linguists are reliant on decent interpretations of language sources, i.e., reconstructing an "earlier linguistic reality" [3, p. 791]. In German studies, there have been many proposals to defining the period of MHG and situating it between Old High and Early New High German [4]. For the purpose of this thesis, I lay my primary focus on the period between 1050 and 1400, which adds a lag of 50 years to a well-established convention [5], [6].

³The totality of these texts that can be subsumed under this specific text-type forms a fundamentally coherent but noticeably diverse mass. While they could be further differentiated, I here bundle them as legal texts. See 2.2.1 for a theoretical differentiation of what constitutes their shared patterns.

⁴Translated definition informally provided by Daniel Luger based on Ahasver von Brandt [7].

dedicated to researching charters is called diplomatics, and it poses an extremely rich methodological tradition, formed over hundreds of years, to evaluate these documents' authenticity. Despite more recent advances in technology and the availability of new methods for studying historical documents, principles and techniques of diplomatics continue to be relevant and widely used in understanding and interpreting these sources.⁵

Given the nature of (historical) legal texts, their structural formulaicity is no surprise [12, p. 69]. While formulaic sequences naturally re-occur, parts of them diverge from the rule and thus form variants. In the past, diplomatic research into respective patterns and their distributions has mostly lacked the means to sustainably detect, measure, and classify formulas and their variation⁶, or as I deem it, flexibility⁷. My work attempts to fill this gap two-fold: first, by exploiting linguistic dispositions in understanding charters as texts; second, by showcasing how the use of statistical and computational approaches can draw a clearer picture of formulaicity and its flexibility in these sources and beyond.

1.1. Motivation

1.1.1. Digital Humanities and Digital History

A driving force of the present research is seen in an agenda constituting the soul of Digital Humanities (DH)⁸ research, i.e., answering 'old questions' with 'new methods'. DH as a research field is located somewhere between a toolset and a mindset.⁹ It has been generating momentum for decades, and it did not halt before the historical sciences. Its spirit has also touched what today is called 'digital history' [16]. This term does not only refer to the extended (and accelerated) acknowledgement, tradition, and processing of historical sources in the digital world, but also their digital scrutiny for hermeneutic purposes (e.g., source criticism [17], [18]).

⁵While the terminology used to describe charters is relatively uniform within a language, it is not so across many since they have different histories of terminology and research paradigms. The terminological toolbox I use to describe my approach and interpretation is primarily German, the main reason being literature that is genealogically and historically closer to the analyzed texts. For the necessity of translating them, I rely on domain expert knowledge and compendia, such as the *Vocabulaire international de la diplomatie (VID)* as provided in its ontology [10], [11].

⁶I emphasize that there exist different understandings of variation that are distinguishable by the linguistically tangible level (and length) of a textual unit that varies as well as the scope of comparison (e.g., different forms of a single text's transmissions [13, p. 47]).

⁷Freely corresponding to Ursula Schulze's "Beweglichkeit" [14, p. 48] based on Paul Zumthor's *Mouvance* (see [15, p. 1539])

⁸Also known as Computational Humanities or Humanities Computing.

⁹As per Matthew Fisher via Jason Heppler's survey on DH definitions:

https://github.com/hepplerj/whatisdigitalhumanities/blob/master/dayofquotes_full.csv.

While there are connections, a strong mutual influence between DH and digital history is debatable. In fact, historians were early independent adopters of computational means to their cause, de facto commencing in the 1940s [19, p. 1], and recording high points in the 1980s and 1990s, with employing novel quantitative approaches [20, p. 169] and exploiting mass digitization of (historical) media [21, p. 44], respectively.¹⁰ Claire Brennan claims "the place of historians within digital humanities is at best peripheral" [23, p. 1], implying linguistic and literary analysis to be at the centre [24, p. 8]. However, it is evident (and inherent) that both content and methods of DH and historical research can easily coincide. For instance, the former causes humanities scholars to establish novel research networks and working groups, building on common ground that is crossing traditional disciplinary borders. Related to the described nexus, this is exemplified in digital Medieval studies: they join forces of historians, linguists, and others, by specifying their scope of research within a given time period [25].¹¹

Independent of disciplinary entanglements, the adoption of digital means has clearly brought advantages that will not leave the scholarly stage. This concerns many facets of historical sources, whether written, visual, or auditory. Nonetheless, some historians still show hesitance in advancing digital history [27]. This reluctance varies across sub-fields of historical research and likely depends on "uneven rates of digitized [re]sources" [24, p. 5]. Digital history is, however, not solely done by analyzing electronic data now remotely available, but also by utilizing more experimental methods. As such, historians of all backgrounds would need to move on (further) from their 'analog logic' [28, p. 31] that are exhibited by the established critical historical methods.

To round things off as per Adam Crymble: "Digital history does not need [more] definitions. It needs histories" [21, p. 161]. It is therefore established that, not only digital history per se, but also its auxiliary sciences are yet to fully embrace and practice novel ways of working with their data. That this need inherently arises in the discipline of diplomacy is a convenient coincidence: according to Reinhard Härtel, diplomatics has always been heavily institutionalized and methodologically conservative, causing the field to adapt new methods only slowly [29, pp. 47-48]. While it is acknowledged that digital preservation of charters is well underway today, he indicates that the field could greatly benefit from more inter-disciplinary and quantitatively encompassing syntheses of past

¹⁰Interestingly, John Unsworth does not generally deem historians as digital pioneers, but specifically medievalists [22].

¹¹This also has the effect that existing areas branch out and specialize even further, e.g., as in the case of German digital medieval studies [26], i.e., institutionally or linguistically. In this context, see also [25].

and present research into charters [29, pp. 49-50].¹² Some scholars remain sceptical about this development's sustainability, yet promising opportunities for diplomatics are seen by lending insights from DH research, with the potential goal of re-evaluating the mismatch between analogue requirements and digital affordances.

1.1.2. From Digital to Distant Diplomatics

To anticipate the digital, great efforts have been made by the diplomatic community since the 1990s to widely incorporate and advance digital (auxiliary) technology [30, p. 452], [31]. This is apparent with the advent of scholarly events in 2004 that put an explicit focus on *digital* diplomatics [32]. Apart from the fact that digital diplomatists moved one step further into the center of the discipline, their matters became much more realistic since computers and their interconnectedness had become ubiquitous in the meantime.

In light of said advances, I conceptually divide them into two categories. The former is concerned with digitization that comprehends these documents as a form of cultural heritage, with the aim of preserving them permanently and hence making them accessible to scholars to work with. The latter deals with processing of the digitized data, with the goal of gaining new insights, as in doing computerized analyses.

The first category of measures taken also comprises building and maintaining digital databases and repositories; parts of what had to be done laboriously by hand is now realized by machines [29, p. 218]. For this, archives (must) open up their charter collections to the (online) public.¹³ By necessity, one consequence is that the work on charters is increasingly becoming more decentralized, and different stakeholders are involved. This also influences which and how features of charters are selected to be preserved; it is generally tried to include transcriptions, abstracts, image scans, and various metadata. The way electronic record keeping is practiced in this domain has been steadily discussed and improved since the early 1990s [34], [35].

The second category, whose tradition is followed by this thesis, refers to the actual transforming, analyzing, and interpreting the data. These steps make the digitization of material more actionable to further research; needs that arise here shape the way how document preservation systems must extend their capabilities of providing data. These

¹²In this context, Reinhard Härtel theorizes large-scale diplomatic replication studies [29, p. 242].

¹³In fact, improved accessibility of these documents has historically proven to be ground-breaking, e.g. the opening of French archives in 1794, or of the Vatican's in 1880 [33, p. 409].

successive strategies of preserving and processing are also reflected in latest attempts of some diplomatists to move From Digital to Distant Diplomatics (DiDip) [36]. *Distant*¹⁴, in contrast to *closely*, is understood as 'reading' large amounts of texts simultaneously to render visible new perspectives on the material. By incorporating applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI), it is hoped to do advanced 'macro-analyses' [38] of 'charter landscapes' [39] that surpass human capabilities.¹⁵

1.2. Literature Review

Since this thesis tackles two different problem areas simultaneously, i.e., the analysis of formulaicity in charters *and* in general, the literature review is divided accordingly. First, an overview of general quantitative research on charters including the underlying corpora is given. Here, the focus is primarily laid on MHG. For more advanced techniques, the scope is increasingly extended to other regions and languages. Second, studies from various fields of research are surveyed that focus on text and attempt to quantify the concept of formulaicity.

1.2.1. Quantitative Research into Charters

This subsection includes studies on MHG charters that put their text at the centre of the investigation, where the goal not necessarily lies in answering diplomatic questions, but in rendering visible (development of) specific language patterns.¹⁶ In this context, I prioritize quantitative ones, with the criteria that a supra-regional (electronic) corpus or edition was employed, that it contains an arbitrary (at least near) three-digit amount of documents, or that the analytical procedure was computational.¹⁷

More comprehensive corpora (and derived analyses) that only marginally include charters are mostly disregarded here, e.g., the Reference Corpus of Middle High German

¹⁴As in Franco Moretti's 'Distant Reading' [37].

¹⁵In the context of diplomatics, a major reason for this need lies in the fact that the number of charters explodes by the beginning of the Late Middle Ages, i.e., the 14th century. Diplomatists therefore focused on periods prior to the said critical one, as it was believed to be more manageable by scrutinizing only smaller or insular collections [40].

¹⁶Research involving a charter's text that is on the cusp of automatic image recognition and processing is deliberately omitted in this thesis.

¹⁷I deem a study quantitative if it is facilitated by an objective surplus of either positive or negative binary classifications, and if it claims to be representative with regards to an object's total population. An advantage of quantitative studies on charters is that the consistency of their interpretations usually correlates with the amount of data [30, p. 458]. See Subsection 2.3.1 on how this relates to the affordances and requirements of language corpora.

(ReM), the Mittelhochdeutsches Textarchiv (MHGTA), and the Middle High German Conceptual Database (MHGCDB). Some smaller collections containing legal texts are the Historischer Südwestdeutscher Sprachatlas (HSS) [41] and the Atlas spätmittelalterlicher Schreibsprachen des niederdeutschen Altlandes und angrenzender Gebiete (ASnA) [42], both having a specific geographic scope with some items shared with the Corpus altdeutscher Originalurkunden (CAO).¹⁸

Subsection 1.2.1.1 contains a brief survey of more general quantitative approaches that include different sets of charter data for statistical analyses. For this part, only work on charters associated with German research traditions are scrutinized.¹⁹ These approaches evidently serve more the need of answering theory-driven work. Subsection 1.2.1.2 contain advanced quantitative (and mostly computational) works that can be described as solving specific tasks, as discussed in Subsection 2.3.2. Especially in this thesis, the latter works allow for reflections on the method rather than contributing to overarching theories.

1.2.1.1. General Approaches

The overwhelming amount of quantitative work has been done on MHG charters of the 13th century, and practically all are on purely linguistic matters. In fact, these sources have proven to be unsurpassed means of studying historical language variation [45, p. 50], [46, p. 153].

The most widely used resource is represented by the CAO, a collection of over 4.000 charters [47].²⁰ Studies using it began in the later 1940s [13]. These works have mostly investigated the correlation of single sound [48], [49], character, or word variations [50], [51] with geographical and temporal distributions as well as document and text categories (in addition to charters).²¹ Quantitative research on date formulas has been notably advanced by Helmut de Boor [53].

A major work built on top of the CAO is represented by the Wörterbuch der mit-

¹⁸With the emergence of such new text collections, some works [43], [44] have critically assessed the quality and benefits of a variety of MHG legal texts to cater linguistic analyses.

¹⁹Analyses do not require full automation to qualify here. Quite the contrary: for instance, the comparative method of reconstructing relations between language varieties requires careful 'manual' handling of the data [3, p. 791].

²⁰Exact details on the many editors and contributors of this corpus must be omitted here.

²¹Correlates of space and time play a crucial role in both classic and modern diplomatic works. See [52] and [30] for further references and reflections of this tradition, also on the extent of statistical and computational methods.

telhochdeutschen Urkundensprache (W^{MU}), i.e., a dictionary with a focus on **MHG** charter-language [54], [55]. It provides means specifically for lexicographic studies.²² Both resources were used to study word formation processes in charter language, including their regional spread [58], [59], [60]. In addition to lexical analyses, Ursula Schulze has investigated syntactical features of charter language, again in conjunction with geographical distribution [13, ch. 4, 5], [61].

Quantitative research for more diplomatic purposes is also posed by the works of Annegret Fiebig, i.e., using concordances to identify **FL** [62], [63], and more recently by Alheydis Plassmann [64], who visualizes geographical charter distributions by issuer, type, and other factors.²³

Two more recent and somewhat summative studies on the quantitative work with charters are presented by Carsten Becker and Oliver Schallert [65], [66]. While their unit of analyses does not drift far from previous works with the **CAO**, they employ a Regular Expression (**RegEx**) stack to explicate variations of words.

1.2.1.2. Advanced Approaches

Apart from applications in Computer Vision (**CV**), especially Handwritten Text Recognition (**HTR**) and Optical Character Recognition (**OCR**) processing, there exists a considerable variety of advanced works related to the processing of charter language.

Of special interest to linguists are the works of Timo Korhakangas et al. [67], [68], who used Latin charter corpora to create tree banks. These are mostly used to investigate Latin syntax variation [69], [70] and aspects of orality [71]. Sandra Waldenberger et al. exercise geolocation by modelling and calculating diachronic spelling variation in Late Medieval German charters contained in the **ReM** based on difference profiles stemming from graphemic normalization mappings. Related to this, Tobias Englmeier employed complex word graphs to allocate **CAO**'s **FL** segments to geographic regions [72, ch. 11].

Advanced analyses that are more of interest to diplomatists lie, for instance, in the field of scribe identification in the sense of authorship attribution. Eveline Leclercq and Mike Kestemont [73] employed text reuse measures to detect the 'identity of hands' [29, p. 252] in 12th century Latin charters. Given the legal nature of charters, considerable

²²A machine-assisted indexing of **MHG** charters was before undertaken by Ulrich Goebel [56]. However, his implementation was heavily critiqued. See [57] on this and other references on early text processing of **MHG** texts.

²³See [30, p. 449] on earlier and similar quantitative works, e.g., Michel Parisse, Benoît-Michel Tock, and Michele Ansani.

work is being done in the area of Named-Entity Recognition (NER) as well. Sergio Torres Aguilar et al. [74] and Pierre Chastang et al [75] used a Conditional Random Field (CRF) to explicate person and location names from Latin charters. Torres Aguilar and Dominique Stutzmann [76] also trained a character-based neural network, i.e., a Bi-Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)-CRF, for extracting entities from French charters. This setup was also repeated for Latin charters [77].

To detect sequences relevant to diplomatists, i.e., form parts of Latin charters, Petra Galuščáková and Lucie Neužilová [78] employed similarity measures and Hidden Markov Models. For the same task, Alina Ostrowski [79] trained Naive Bayes Classifiers. The team around Michael Gervers used recurrent strings to identify FL sequences that corresponded to the dating of English medieval charters from the Documents of Early England Data Set (DEEDS) project. They thus narrowed down their age using statistical estimate and smoothing measures [80], [81], [82]. Notable work is currently done by Marijn Koolen et al. who summarize repetitive language via clustering, and use different language models to capture sequential variability in historical legal texts [83], [84], [85].

1.2.2. Quantitative Research into Formulaicity

This section surveys some quantitative approaches of making the phenomenon of formulaicity tangible beyond the scope of charters. The main focus of this selected overview lies on structural approaches that have been applied on language data by linguists, and which have definitely gained a foothold in their discipline.²⁴

In connection to my analysis in Chapter 4, I suggest understanding formulaicity primarily as the result of high structural recurrence, and formulaic flexibility as the (conditional) tendency of structures to (not) alternate. Since formulaicity and formulaic flexibility are tightly connected, I discuss them jointly. Further, I anticipate the different perspectives on formulaicity found in Chapter 2 by subsuming them as questions, on various levels of structure, not meaning. At the start of an investigation into formulaicity of given texts, I ask: What is in them? Or better using terminology of Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL): How are they "composed" [87, p. 48] in terms of frequency and distribution, and relative to others?

²⁴Approaches that include an explicit reference to formulaicity or concepts thereof are prioritized. Where deemed appropriate, other approaches are taken into account as well. However, treating multiple definitions of FL and their implicit references equally would result in a candidate list that is not in the scope of this thesis. I must hence disregard similar approaches from the fields of data mining and pattern recognition. See [86] on the cross-disciplinary explanatory power in the face of frequency distributions in language.

1.2.2.1. Recurrence and Persistence

The first strand of approaches asks: How much structural recurrence is there in a text, and which recurrences are most persistent? What is a text's constancy [88]? To answer these questions, recurrence can be investigated on and across different levels of segmentation. For instance, how many words are in a text (tokens), and how many are different (types)? Further, how do they interrelate (e.g., Type-Token Ratio (**TTR**))? For word level recurrence, prime concepts entertained in language research are found in the nexus of Lexical Diversity (**LD**), richness, or density.²⁵ However, their indices are all used in connection with the analysis of word repetition in and across texts [92], and as in [93], **LD** can be used as an umbrella term, given that it implies the phenomenon can be gradual.

A first few indices capturing this diversity have been formulated before the 1960s [94]. Over time, they have been used for a variety of studies into repetition in language, with some recent application in language testing and assessment [95], language learning and education [96], [97], speech impediment research [98], but also more computationally, such as machine translation [99]. Fundamentally, they rely on word count and repetition in and across texts. This approach can be extended as to understand a text's composure not by the unit of words, but by n -grams, where n can represent more than uni-grams. Multiple ways have been found to generate structurally repetitive sequences longer and more diverse than what is typically worked with in **FL** research. Some of these are 'phrase-frames' (n -grams with 1-skip [100]), 'skip-grams' (n -grams with optional k -skips [101] [102]), and 'conc-grams' (bi-directional n -grams with optional k -skips [103]).²⁶

1.2.2.2. Recurrence and Alternation

The second strand of approaches asks: Which are the most likely alternations to these recurrent units, and how flexible or cohesive are they? In other words, what is their "potential of collocability" [104, p. 328], and what is their "choice" [105, p. 52]? These options are related to slots of a longer, otherwise fixed sequence, where parameters of the interchangeable slot, e.g., length, position, quality, are determined by the research motivation.²⁷

²⁵Due to its cross-disciplinary history, this terminology has to this day not been satisfactorily disambiguated. Compare [89], [90] and [91] on this.

²⁶Notably, while implemented in some online corpus querying systems, the exact algorithm of conc-gramming is not fully public.

²⁷See Subsection 2.2.3 on some more parameters often considered in language research.

Several ways have been found to calculate the association (or salience [106]) between grams and, based on this, to highlight and generate (new) alternating sequences. While some have looked at alternations and merges based on semantic, syntactic, or lexicogrammatical categories (e.g., collocations [107], [108] or sum-grams [109]), several works have done so solely with structure. These include 'tiled n -grams' [110], 'collocational chains' [111], and 'collocades' [112], where all of them are the result of some greedy score-based n -gram merge²⁸ algorithm. A related approach is proposed by Alexander Wahl and Stefan Gries [114], which is currently developed further by Marijn Koolen et al. [83] [84], [85].

These sequences rely on some measure of a subset n -gram co-occurrence likelihood²⁹ and, to different extents, take into account (relative) type and token frequencies and distributions given a corpus or a reference.³⁰ Classic measures taken from information theory are relative entropy [117] and (pointwise) Mutual Information (MI) [118] as an expression of surprise, coincidence, or informativeness [119]. Some of these have been used to identify lexical bundles in legal texts [120], and they also gained traction in the analysis of historical German shallow syntax [121]. More specific measures for linguistics are 'lexical attraction' [122], 'lexical gravity' [111], [123], or 'valency' [124].³¹ Although only indirectly connected to formulaicity [129], a noteworthy approach in corpus linguistics is keyword analysis, i.e., calculating frequencies relative to some distributional measure, e.g., word count [130], which can form the basis for finding collocation networks [131].

1.3. Research Questions and Objectives

As described, a decent amount of scholarly work has been done on both the quantitative analysis of (MHG) charters as well as the identification and explication of FL patterns across domains. However, some factors have been less regarded in the research. For instance, formulaicity in historical documents has received little attention from schol-

²⁸While mergers are becoming increasingly popular, it is not fully clear whether a greater n can always be desired and valuable. At least for exploring the phraseological vocabulary of historical legal texts, it can be surmised that longer sequences are especially interesting [113].

²⁹Depending on the type of sequence and measurement, this can also be understood as slot-filling or transition probability [115]

³⁰Research into (ranking) longest common sub-strings — different from sub-sequences — has been researched already in the 1970s [116].

³¹Many more statistical measures used across linguistics are found in the works of Stefan Gries, e.g., [125], [126], [127]. See also [128] for an overview of multi-word identification and processing from the viewpoint of Computational Linguistics.

ars; neither its flexibility nor distribution over time, across, and within texts and text categories have been quantitatively scrutinized much. I take the amalgam of previous studies, the resulting research gaps, as well as the general need to differentiate between formulaicities as a basis to triangulate the problem and formulate my research questions:

RQ1. How can formulaicity be defined?

- (a) How is formulaicity viewed in diplomatics and (computational) linguistics?
- (b) Do their views differ, and if so, how?

RQ2. How can formulaicity be measured?

- (a) How formulaic are charters compared to other texts?
- (b) Has formulaicity in charters changed over time, and if so, how?

RQ3. How can formulas be identified?

- (a) What are the most frequent or significant formulas across charters?
- (b) How are formulas distributed across different sections of charters?

RQ4. How can formulaic flexibility be measured?

- (a) How can similar formulas be identified and quantified?
- (b) To what extent can formulaic language be predicted?

By answering these research questions, this thesis aims to achieve several overarching objectives. Firstly, it seeks to enhance the understanding and measurement of formulaicity in **MHG** texts. Secondly, it aims to assess how linguistic and computational methodology can facilitate knowledge relevant to diplomatics. To achieve these objectives, I use a charter corpus to semi-automatically discover **FL** patterns, explore their distributions, and assess their flexibility. The corpus is prepared and enriched for analysis using a combination of manual and automated methods, and various techniques from computational linguistics are applied to the data. Through this process, this thesis expands the range of **MHG** charters studied, and sheds light on the structure and content of these documents. The employed methods are data-driven and hence practically language-agnostic since they rely on little to no linguistic knowledge of the texts, except the graphemic level [14, pp. 67-68].³² Notably, instead of subjecting any concrete hypotheses to scrutiny, I experiment with different techniques in the manner of an Exploratory Data Analysis (**EDA**). As such, my analysis is fundamentally a program demonstration of quantifying formulaicity and its flexibility. Methods and results thus serve for further discussion and research, especially in the face of diplomatic tasks.

³²It is acknowledged here that, in the sense of Emily Bender [132], no analysis of language can ever be completely language-agnostic. In my analysis, this is especially visible when normalizing the data and evaluating the results.

1.4. Outline

The theoretical background presented in Chapter 2 offers a deepened understanding of formulaicity across multiple fields, which adds to the reasons for subsequent analyses. Each subsection therein corresponds to a scientific area, and I give additional information to better understand how formulaicity is conceptualized in each. This provides multiple theoretical answers to RQ1(a) and more methodological ones to the others. At the end of that Chapter, I reflect on how disciplines and scholars differ in their understanding of formulaicity as an answer to RQ1(b).

Chapter 3 describes the exact scope [133] of my analysis, including references to used corpora, data, code, and libraries. Here, I showcase the exact data (pre-)processing pipelines and sketch how the methodology in Chapter 4 is used to answer my research questions. In Chapter 4, I describe some results of my program and support them visually. Lastly, I summarize my findings to answer the research questions in Chapter 5. I thereby critically reflect on my methodology and remark on possible future research.

2. Theoretical Foundations

Given the benefits of multiple theoretical vantage points, I outline three perspectives that can be taken on the phenomenon of formulaicity.³³ Such a perspective corresponds to a theoretical model, i.e., representing a (past) reality by systematic simplification [135], [136]. To show how stacking such models helps in better understanding the subject, I outline fundamentals to each perspective that can be attributed to scholarly fields and their different methodological approaches. The order in which I discuss them is related to a perceived proximity to the data (i.e., charters) on the one hand and naturally follows a path to increased quantification in their approaches on the other hand.³⁴

In Section 2.1, I give a brief outline of the different manifestations and identities of charters as well as how they were created and transmitted. I continue with explaining what features of charters are typically of interest to scholars. Closing in on charters' texts, their language and style is described. I end with carefully dissecting how diplomatists (indiscriminatingly) use terminology in the nexus of formulaicity, to better pinpoint to which aspect of formulaicity my research adds most. Also, I include some historical developments of this field specifically since it represents the domain 'hosting' the material.

Then, some of the diplomatic findings are contrasted with linguistic perspectives in Section 2.2 in order to assess how they can be generalized. For this, I lay the theoretical foundation for charters as an own text type and explain their performative character by the means of linguistic pragmatics. Furthermore, I picture the role which formulaicity

³³Admittedly, the distinction between these perspectives is made only intuitively. Specifically for linguistic and computational perspectives, there is a natural overlap due to the fact that the interest of linguists in applying computational methods has been steadily increasing over the last decades. However, I argue that, due to their historical development, both fields cater different scientific communities with different practical requirements, i.e., classical linguistics being more interested in the theory, and computational more in the method. In this context, I hence deem an approach to pinning down repetitive language and formulaicity as computational especially if it requires considerable computing power, e.g., calculating word vectors. Moreover, I understand computational linguistics as a simultaneous referent for corpus linguistics, with quantitative linguistics somewhere in its vicinity, mainly due to its increasingly similar methodology. Compare [134] on this very point.

³⁴For the purpose of this overview, I put formulaicity of medium-length sequences at the center, i.e., **FL** on word and sentence level, and eventually how it would relate to characters and texts.

plays in the context of register studies and legal linguistics.

Finally in Section 2.3, I remark on some fundamental points in grasping text as data. I highlight how understanding research problems as processing tasks can add a hermeneutically advantageous layer to the analysis of formulaicity in charters. As such, a digression on past and present text modelling and vectorization practices is necessary.

2.1. Classical Diplomatics

As in the introductory definition, charters can be referred to as diplomas. Latin *diploma* is derived from a Greek verb meaning 'to double'. It originally referred to joined tablets and later more general to (multiple) documents. While during the Middle Ages the term was rarely used in reference to charters, it gained popularity in the 16th century with the increased spread of Humanist Latin [137, p. 37]. The first use of 'diplomatics' signifying a discipline is attributed to the Benedictine monk Jean Mabillon in 1681 [33, p. 405].

Engaging in diplomatics gained momentum in 17th century Europe, in response to large-scale disputes over the authenticity and truthfulness of legal claims (e.g., in the Cabinet Wars). Later in the 19th century, the field was particularly developed in German-speaking countries in order to facilitate a better understanding of (their) legal and political history (e.g., the aftermath of the Holy Roman Empire). As a result, institutions and societies dedicated to the study and edition of charters were founded, and traditions of passing them down consolidated [137, p. 37].

The main subject area of diplomatics begins with the transmission of medieval papal and royal charters in the course of the 6th century. The beginning of their end is allocated at the verge between Medieval and Modern times, in the 16th century, given that the function of charters was transferred to and surpassed by other forms of expression exhibiting legal character [138, p. 16]. Accordingly, the interests of legal scholars in charters diminished, and those of historians rose [33, p. 406]. While diplomatics is often understood as a discipline on its own, it is also considered an auxiliary science given its importance to adjacent fields. Indeed, it has even gained the status of a 'foundational' [139] science to the study of history.

2.1.1. Charter Types and Traditions

Against the backdrop of diplomatics as a 'seam between law and history'³⁵, charters constitute a distinct type of historical source as it is of high value to more than one discipline. In this context, 'source' is understood as a generic term for a testimony that can be used to research history [142]. Given their specificity and reliability, charters often serve the function of supervising other testimonies; they embody the best option of assessing their historical truth and hence significance [33, p. 406], [143, p. 46].

Given that charters are texts that cover a variety of different legal cases, they differ in how they were created, used, and passed on. At least in the German tradition, they are typically divided into three categories, i.e., imperial and royal, papal, or private.³⁶ Imperial and royal charters are usually further divided into diplomas and mandates, their difference being that the former's validity is practically permanent and the latter's is temporary — this duality exists in papal charters as well, i.e., privileges vs. litterae [138, pp. 13-14]. Private charters hold the greatest variety of sources, e.g., cases advanced by (arch) bishops, monasteries and convents, dukes and earls, (lower) nobility, cities and citizens, universities, or public notaries.

This established tripartite differentiation, which builds on a document's historical perceived notion of legal quality or validity, for conceptual reasons continues to be controversial among diplomatists [138, p. 15], [137, pp. 82-83]. One is because, for the purpose of today's scholarly inquiry, charters are only sustainably classified across multiple dimensions. In fact, they can be distinguished further by their legal duration, their legal function, their form, their legal area and topic, their material, among others [138, p. 14].

Depending on the type of charter, different persons and institutions are involved with a charter's genesis. In general, an issuer (the person whose legal will is expressed) addresses an act in connection with the recipient (the contract partner that mostly legally profits and keeps the original), sometimes attested by witnesses (a qualified group of people for the purpose of later provability). This process is usually facilitated by including a scribe to prepare and execute the writing. However, issuer and scribe can be a single person, which is often the case in private charters [29, pp. 22-23].

The standard location of issuing was the chancery. These bodies became increasingly professionalized from the 12th century onward, and starting in the Late Middle Ages,

³⁵As per Martin Faber [140, p. 249] based on Maciej Dorna's work [141].

³⁶The charters covered in this work as well as the literature dissecting them is naturally Euro-centric. However, given some generalization, the nature of these documents — "a single unifying concept" [144, p. 128] — has shown to be more universal (and trans-cultural) than previously assumed [145], [146].

(non-private) chanceries acted more and more independently [137, p. 55]. While chancellors were preoccupied with other tasks, the charter's legal instrumentation³⁷ could be undertaken by dedicated notaries [138]. As de facto institutions, chanceries became incrementally more powerful and influential in authenticating and transmitting charters.³⁸

As can be deduced, there are different historical forms through which (the content of) a charter stands the test of time.³⁹ For this, diplomatists distinguish between a charter being either handed down as original or copy. Further, one can differentiate between documents posing an actual legal effect and those only serving administrative purposes. For instance, documents often only survived in a form of drafts. These were normally destroyed after the original had been executed (or renewed) [137, p. 41].

Copies vary depending on their purpose: they can aim at an original's duplication, a (partial) transcription or a translation. Accordingly, they can be organized by features resulting from conflicting interests between issuer and recipient (e.g., the charter's depository) and by their degree of credibility in representing the legal content (e.g., the means of authentication) [138, p. 104].

A major form of transcribed tradition is the *transsumpt*, in which a text of a past charter is inserted into a more recent one and populated with means of certifying the legal matter, with the effect of taking a liability. Another one is the *vidimus*, which is similar to the *transsumpt* except that it only affirms the existence and quality of a charter's literal content, not its validity [29, pp. 28-30].

For administrative purposes, charters were organized systematically already early. Major collection types are registers and cartularies; the former established by the issuer, the latter by the recipient.⁴⁰ Both contain records of (copied) charters in the form of abstracts or summaries [138, p. 106].⁴¹

³⁷*L' instrumentation* as per the VID [147, p. 23].

³⁸Notably, such notarial and ecclesiastical establishments would regularly clash in their race for influence, starting in the High Middle Ages [29, p. 149].

³⁹Here, I understand 'historical' as an opposite to systematic transmissions that were produced (much) later, e.g., scholarly editions. A decent overview of European charter editions is provided with the *Cartae Europae Medii Aevi* (CEMA) project [148], [149].

⁴⁰See Subsection 2.1.3.2 on more referents of these and similar collections.

⁴¹Both the keeping and maintaining of registers and cartularies books were truly consistent only in isolated institutions [137, p. 41]. This fact reflects in the inability of diplomatists to formulate definitions of such collection systems that are both encompassing *and* impeccable. For instance, compare entries on *register* in the VID [147]. Also, see Subsection 2.1.3.2 on the variety of naming conventions for formulaic templates.

2.1.2. Charter Modalities and Diplomatic Units

The formation of trans-regional medieval charter standard modalities (or characteristics) lasted until the end of the 12th century [144, p. 127].⁴² First, through this development, and second, by a sophisticated terminology stemming from diplomatics, it is possible to compare an individual specimen with its assumed prototype. By designating the features of a charter, one can make visible its (lack of) quality: the unjustified existence or absence of certain characteristics could even render it a forgery.

A charter's typical document review foresees an analysis of internal and external features [151, pp. 45-48]. The former include the document's material, preservation status, layout and format, font, graphic signs as well as means of authentication [138, ch. 5]; compare Figure 2.1. The latter concerns the charter's textual (and legally relevant) content, i.e., 'formal elements of the legal act'⁴³, the vocabulary, register, and style [138, ch. 6].

Figure 2.1.: Selected 14th century charters of different types, regions, and languages.
(a) A private charter recording the ownership of an estate. Adapted from <https://www.monasterium.net/mom/AT-WStLA/HAUrk/174/charter>
(b) A royal charter confirming rights to an apanage. Adapted from https://www.monasterium.net/mom/IlluminierteUrkunden/1375-03-03_Paris/charter
(c) A papal charter decreeing the schedule of celebrations. Adapted from https://www.monasterium.net/mom/IlluminierteUrkundenKurie/1389-11-09_Muenchen/charter

Based on features investigated, one must agree on which of these can be purposefully isolated. This poses a challenge that is grounded in the fact that a charter poses multiple identities depending on context and interpretation, e.g., as legal act, as copy, or as im-

⁴²Arguably, similar documents as well as efforts in formalizing them have existed before the Middle Ages; such legal precursors as well as their associated profession certainly had an influence on what later constitutes Medieval charters; see [150, pp. 6, 74].

⁴³*Éléments formels des actes* as per the VID [147, p. 37].

age.⁴⁴ In addition, these identities have taken shape for different purposes and reception contexts. As such, it is difficult to determine context-independently what the signifier to the term 'charter' is. The consequence lies in agreeing on the 'diplomatic unit'⁴⁵ of analysis, that is, to clarify, on the one hand, what is referred to by 'the charter' and, on the other hand, to examine it with an adequate methodology.

For the given occasion, the charter's (transmitted) text, i.e., the depiction of a legal context that is found on a charter's *recto* side — as visible in Figure 2.1 —, builds the unit of analysis.⁴⁶ More practically, I refer to the VID as result of debate as to what constitutes a charter's content. The so-called tenor comprises the whole framework of the charter's written act; it can be reduced to three groups: the protocol, the text, and the eschatocole [147, p. 53]. As such, other textual elements outside of the tenor — regardless of the type of transmission — are excluded from this study (e.g., notes on a charter's back or *plica*; compare Figures 2.1b, 2.1c).

2.1.3. Formulaicity: Diplomatic Perspectives

From the viewpoint of diplomatics, formulaicity appears to be largely explained by its function in communication. As such, it describes communicative occurrences that follow (contextually) expected templates whose emergence is usage-based and sometimes required by legal customs. I argue that formulaicity in diplomatic research either alludes to the specificity of individual utterances and their dynamic performative character, or to the specificity of regular patterns and their static descriptive character. These two are explained in the following subsections.

2.1.3.1. Formulaic Language

Formulaic language in charters is noticeable due to the operation principles underlying their individual expressions. As described before, a charter is strongly connected to the actual legal act that is (pragmatically) expressed. By the means of a written record, a conceptually oral announcement becomes reproducible, rendering it a law that can evidently outlast its primal reception.⁴⁷ Language use in charters, in contrast to other

⁴⁴See [152, p. 140] for a thorough conceptual deconstruction of a charter's identity.

⁴⁵A keyword in debates held at the Digital Diplomats '22 conference [153].

⁴⁶An original text usually is written on one single dedicated sheet [29, p. 243].

⁴⁷The exact relation between legal act and record depends on the type of charter. For instance, a record with the sole purpose of proof can be created after the act, whereas a transaction usually requires immediacy [29, p. 25].

historical text types, is characterized by semantically augmenting otherwise common terms, and enriching respective utterances with non-standard structural and stylistic devices [14, p. 48], [154]. This process makes legal statements more performative and authentic in their (ritualistic) reception [138, p. 143]. It can even result in the attribution of a magical function to the document itself, which is partly related to the fact that medieval charters were often endowed with religious elements [29, p. 314].⁴⁸ In the context of imperial and royal charters, Heinrich Fichtenau even went so far as to claim that many charters could be understood as instruments of propaganda⁴⁹, with the *arenga* section as *captatio benevolentiae* posing the center of ideology [160, p. 32].⁵⁰

While language in charters widely follows specific patterns, they pose evident derivations that vary in their distribution, which, as per the introduction, I deem to be formulaic flexibility. Ground work for explaining this phenomenon was done by Ursula Schulze [14, pp. 70-71], who argues that it exists due to the complex prerequisites exhibited by the text type's actual use. As such, charters are influenced by inherent oral traditions of transmitting information.⁵¹ They require structural (prototypical) models ('macro-structures' with 'keywords') that can be enacted as variations due to conditions of individual legal cases and contexts: the micro-structure varies across regions, institutions, and individual groups, with the possibility of significant mutual influences [14, p. 53]. In diplomatics, the individual phrasing in charters is described as the result of the *dictamen* [147, p. 82], i.e., how the scribe produces a charter's text based on the issuer's dictation [29, p. 34].

2.1.3.2. Formulaic Units

In addition to a characterization of textual formulaicity based on its effect upon reception, it can as well be explained by its use in referring to regularized structures.⁵² By

⁴⁸In the context of charters, see [155, p. 12] pragmatic and performative aspects; see [156] for a differentiation of symbolic mechanisms in the document's life-cycle; see [157] on rituals.

⁴⁹See [158] for an overview, with special reference to [159]

⁵⁰Interestingly, Heinrich Fichtenau found inspiration to this approach in philological studies; his work laid the foundation for studies not only on a charter's verbal rhetoric, but also its visual [161, p. 272].

⁵¹Charters are therefore characterized by what is called conceptual orality. Some evidence for this was found for Latin charters [71]. Related to this, Sonja Zeman [162, p. 276] stresses that conceptual orality is not equal to conceptualized orality, the former being generated more naturally, the latter artificially. However, since there is no reliable way of knowing what orality *really* was like in the past, it is impossible to determine the structural relation between said oralities for historical texts, only to hesitantly estimate their effect upon reception. See also [163] on the relation between oral and written culture in medieval texts.

⁵²Notably, a charter's repetitive elements are not limited to the text, but concern external features as well, such as layout and character spacing [29, p. 242].

taking a closer look and carefully disentangling the terminology associated with **FL**, it is possible to distinguish between multiple categories (or as I also deem it, units⁵³) of how formulaicity is referred to in diplomatics. For this, a wide range of diplomatic sources are consulted, e.g., classics, (modern) surveys, and case studies.

The first and arguably largest category of referents of formulaicity are 'forms and form parts'. As per Subsection 2.1.2, a form contains formal elements of the legal act. Depending on their type and context, charters differ in their elements, their order, as well as the amount of text dedicated to each. Core parts in a typical order are the following [138, ch. 6]:

- intitulatio: naming of the issuer
- inscriptio: naming of the recipient
- arenga: reasoning of the individual issue and case
- narratio: description of the legal situation and involved entities
- dispositio: explanation of the legal act
- sanctio: legal consequences in case of non-compliance
- signum: signature and authentication
- datatio: naming of dates for *actum* (act) and *datum* (issuance)

While together they embody a fixed apparatus, its parts received different attention both then and now, given that they had various functions and were correspondingly elastic depending on context. Due to a different (relative) importance of form components, specific research traditions have emerged over time.

The second category is 'form (parts) abstractions'; it refers to alternations, generalizations, or sub-specifications of the diplomatic form or its parts, often coined by the equivalent part's plural or some derivation. These abstractions are observed to be not just simple translations of a Latin original. Instead, they appear to generate new either overarching or even more specific labels for form parts, and effectively generalize differently than the 'classic' form. Their existence is proof that the conventional way of describing a charter's form is not sufficient to adequately represent every charter's content. Some of the most consistently used and/or conceptually striking abstractions in alphabetical order are:

- Dating formula — "Datierungs"- [164, p. 324], [165, p. 12]; "Datumsformel" [29, p. 36]
- Ending formula — "Schlussformel" [164, p. 295]
- Enforcement formula — "Vollziehungsformel" [165, p. 48], [29, p. 55]

⁵³As in *unit of analysis* or *diplomatic unit*.

- Greeting formula — "Grußformel" [164, p. 339], [165, p. 17], [29, p. 36]
- Initiating formula — "Eingangs"- [165, p. 13]; "Arengeformel" [164, p. 341]
- Intervention formula — "Interventionsformel" [165, p. 13]
- Oath formula — "Eidesformel" [165, p. 13], [29, p. 269]
- Penalty⁵⁴ formula — "Poen"- [165, p. 31], [29, p. 38]; "Strafformel" [164, p. 358]
- Scribe formula — "Schreiberformel" [164, p. 319], [165, p. 13]
- Signature formula — "Signatur"- [165, p. 43]; "Signumformel" [166, p. 208]
- Witness formula — "Zeugenformel" [167, p. 13]

While diplomatists might be aware how these abstractions can manifest and individually differ, this list makes it apparent that they can logically and structurally overlap. For instance, it is unclear whether the referral as an initiating formula can also designate an arenga and a publicatio; also, an ending formula might possibly indicate a charter's whole eschatocolle without naming it explicitly.

The third category covers 'formulaic segments', i.e., referents to (short) **FL** sequences that are not necessarily typical realizations of a charter's form or dictation. They do not have to cater legal needs and may also be used by scholars as more general descriptors of language in charters, i.e., a form of meta-discourse to draw attention on the subject matter of **FL** in charters. In contrast to traditional form parts, they are nearly resistant to being conclusively defined. Admittedly, they bear an even higher risk of ambiguity in (my) idiomatic translations. Some of the most common segment referents are:

- Formula statements — "Formel-Aussage" [167, p. 14]
- Form parts — "Formel" [29, p. 467]
- Formulaic contractions — "mit formelhaften Verkürzungen" [168, p. 134]
- Formulaic parts — "formelhafte Bestandteile" [29, p. 30]
- Idiomatic phrases — "Formel"⁵⁵ [169, p. 434], [170]
- Recurring formulas — "wiederkehrende Formeln" [29, p. 309]
- Wordings — "Formulierung" [29, p. 30]

This category of understanding formulaicity is particularly relevant to this thesis, as it closely aligns with how **FL** is approached in (computational) linguistics. However, the role and value of formulaicity in diplomatics is highly ambiguous. On one hand, a formula exhibits specific effects simply by existing, and can be used to normatively classify legal documents. On the other hand, some formulas are so common that they

⁵⁴*Poenae* as per the **VID** [147, p. 64]

⁵⁵Here, *Formel* has different signified words than 'form parts'.

become meaningless and exist only to fulfill a legal formal expectation.⁵⁶

The fourth category is formed by references to collections of, as I deem it, 'formulaic templates'. These references can either be more historical or more contemporary, i.e., for medieval scribes to consult or material for diplomatists to research. Moreover, they can be further specified to specific form parts, adding to the notion of formulas being a charter's building blocks [138, p. 103]. I translate them as follows:

- Chancery handbooks — "Kanzleihandbuch" [171, p. 751]
- Form aids — "Formularbehelfe" [172]
- Form collections — "Formularsammlungen" [29, p. 468]
- Formula assets — "Formelgut" [172, p. 90]
- Formula collections — "Formelsammlungen" [138, p. 161]
- "Formulae" [173], [174], [175]; "Formularii" [34, p. 10]
- Formularies — "Formularbuch" [176], "Formelbuch" [172, p. 68]
- Form templates — "Formularvorlage" [29, p. 468]
- Letter plates — "Briefsteller" [177]
- Volumes — "Verzeichnis" [178]

Especially in multilingual contexts, the use of terms referring to formulaicity appears highly ambiguous. Admittedly, this can be problematic due to translation processes. However, they are so in isolated languages as well. In German for instance, the degree to which *Formular* and *Formel* are interchangeable when used as composite to collections is non-trivial.⁵⁷

Given this differentiation of formulaic units, it is evident that formulaicity has a wide range of meanings. Judging from the review of diplomatic literature, the respective terminology is not (yet) explicitly standardized or disambiguated. As a consequence, different understandings of formulaicity may clash already within diplomatics itself. This can be problematic if charters are taken up in other (Medieval) studies. Defining it, however, enables one to isolate and reflect on specific meanings of formulaicity in the diplomatic sense, as demonstrated here.

It also becomes apparent that diplomatists have a domain-specific understanding of for-

⁵⁶This observation is based on the inspection of charter transcriptions, where the formulaic parts that are deemed 'empty' are often omitted and replaced with dots or hyphens as placeholders.

⁵⁷Ludwig Rockinger already implied in the late 19th century that references to these templates lack clear naming conventions: "[diese] Muster [...], oder wie sie sonst noch heissen mögen" [179, p. 136]. For some entities, this problem is ongoing — especially in multilingual contexts. For instance, compare entries on *register* in the VID [147].

mulaic flexibility. For instance, a charter's text consists of different sections, where both the sections and its constituents are usually taken from prefabricated text inventories. Among other factors, the individual legal case thus determines how these building blocks are put together in order to serve a specific pragmatic purpose. These modular properties are also illuminated in the next section.

2.2. Classical Linguistics

First, to complement the diplomatic view on charter as specific (sub-)types of documents, I outline less-specific linguistic approaches to text and text types.⁵⁸ Second, as a response to Subsection 2.1.3.1 and the performative character of charters, I briefly outline how pragmatics is conceptualized in linguistics, and explain its relation to semantics. Then, as a response to Subsection 2.1.3.2, equivalent linguistic perspectives on formulaicity and formulaic flexibility are given.

2.2.1. Text and Text Types

While it is simple to pin down the meaning of *word* or *sentence*, defining 'a text' is more complicated.⁵⁹ A major reason for this complication is the fact texts have less concrete (graphemic) conventions than smaller units: they can vary considerably, e.g., concerning length, style, or lexis. Text linguists have come up with several ways to make the qualitative dimensions of texts more describable.⁶⁰ As such, they can be classified by their similarities and differences. One ends up with types of language that are specifically shaped towards an imagined (prototypical) form. In the case of text, the results are text types (or text categories). But by which exact aspects are texts compared?

In text linguistics, there exist two prominent and somewhat conflicting approaches for defining a text and deriving categories, both gaining momentum from the 1980s onward. The first focuses on the text's content. For this, Robert-Alain de Beaugrande and Wolfgang Dressler have formulated several features of textuality (e.g., coherence and co-

⁵⁸Defining (a) text was not always a primary task of linguists and speech philosophers, and it is still a secondary of scholars from other disciplines [180, p. 2]. A formative piece on the coming-together of different text understandings — especially in the DH context — is presented by Patrick Sahle, who stresses the importance of finding not one universal, but a contextually adequate and well-integrated definition [181, pp. 45, 60].

⁵⁹Etymologically, 'text' is derived from Latin *textus*, meaning succession, connection, or continuation, and *texere*, meaning weaving, braiding, building [1, p. 619], [182].

⁶⁰Notably, I primarily outline the European tradition of text linguistics [180, ch. 1], and the German one at that. See [183, ch. 13] for surveys on other regions.

hesion) that facilitate such a classification. However, the authors admit that, ultimately, the ways how we actually use text and how texts serve human interaction are more decisive for such classifications [184, p. 3].⁶¹ This bridges the gap to the second approach, which puts a text’s function at the center. Accordingly, Klaus Brinker defined a text as the sum of complex linguistic patterns which have emerged within a given (historical) linguistic community to cater for specific communicative needs [185, p. 118].

Within this dichotomy, I prefer the functional approach to the content-based one. One reason is that this coincides with how diplomatists conceptualize the function of legal texts, i.e., a means of as communication shaped by specific contexts in which they are created and used. It is also consistent with the functional approach as it stresses the interplay between linguistic patterns and the communicative needs of the community in question, e.g., copying from formulaic templates as a means of authentication [62, p. 278]. Another reason is the fact that content-based text classification has a larger interpretative scope.⁶² Consequently, it is advisable to put a text’s function at the centre, and then jointly analyze how structural features are functionally supportive [187, p. 3].

In sum, a text can be described as a functional linguistic unit that is coherent and meaningful, both structurally and conceptually, and texts can be characterized by the inherent functions that they execute [186, pp. 275-276]. This view is in line with how diplomatists differentiate documents, i.e., based on similarities and differences of internal and external features, in conjunction with functions derived from legal affordances. This gives an insight into other (textual) aspects that Medieval scribes have had in mind when producing charters as well as what diplomatists scrutinize today. Also, the outline of how linguists understand texts and text types also makes more visible that charters pose a form of medieval literature [188] that can be classified as an own text-type [189], [13, p. 23], [190, p. 68].

2.2.2. Pragmatics and Performativity

As described in Subsection 2.1.3, charters contain performative language, which can evidently nest well in FL. This can be well-explained by resorting to the fundamentals of two linguistic sub-fields, i.e., pragmatics and semantics. Semantics is concerned

⁶¹Indeed, they describe texts as fundamentally ‘communicative occurrences’ [184, p. 3], which, by definition, puts a heavy focus on its functional character.

⁶²In particular, it implicitly separates text-internal and text-external properties for both the situation of production and of analysis [186, p. 281]. When fully committing to this approach, it would be necessary to distinguish between semantically and pragmatically relevant knowledge, which can be problematic, as alluded to in the upcoming section 2.2.2.

with meaning in a preferably objective and logic manner. Pragmatics rather deals with context-dependent meaning, and how it is co-constructed through the knowledge, intentions, and efforts of a communication's participants [191, pp. 197, 368].⁶³

Paul Kroeger [193, p. 5] claims that, beside words and sentences, which represent meaning more reliably, we also communicate via forms of 'utterances', i.e., realizations of meaning for specific situations. In essence, this distinction reflects the relation between semantics and pragmatics, namely that (sequences of) words either carry meaning context-independently or context-dependently. Another way of expressing their relation stems from Gerald Gazdar: "pragmatics = meaning – truth conditions" [194, p. 2], where 'meaning' acts as a semantic 'universal frame of discourse' [195, p. 236].⁶⁴

A major area of pragmatics research is concerned with speech acts, i.e., manifestations of performative language — "how to do things with words" [197].⁶⁵ Performativity hence refers to an action that is being achieved symbolically by means of an utterance, beyond the language being uttered, e.g., a declaration, a plea, a promise [186, p. 207]. More than 50 years ago, several theorists have come up with ways of classifying such acts, and dividing them further. One is John Searle's [198] distinction between a proposition (a statement), an illocution (a call to action), and a perlocution (a reaction). Notably, every utterance has some illocutionary force, the degree of which is up to interpretation [199, p. 150].

While it has been exercised extensively for decades, speech act theory has also been heavily criticised, often by the allegation of its models being too simplistic in representing the reality of language use.⁶⁶ Furthermore, the validity or applicability of speech act theory is especially being questioned when exercised quantitatively.⁶⁷ Nonetheless, perhaps exactly due to its simplicity, speech act theory has prevailed: Even if its model is flawed, it is still helpful in making aware of past and present performative language.

Coming back to the semantics-pragmatics duality: one of its premises is that context-

⁶³Etymologically, 'semantics' is derived from Ancient Greek *σημα*, meaning sign or character [192, p. 1323]; 'pragmatics' is derived from *πράγμα*, meaning action or work [192, p. 1230].

⁶⁴See [196, ch. 1] on the role of conventions in the nexus of semantics and pragmatics.

⁶⁵While pragmatics often is exemplified with samples of natural oral language, the concept of speech acts is not limited to speech.

⁶⁶The problems of formally describing pragmatic meaning are well-known at least since 1979 [200]. For a more recent instance, see [201] on the problem of meaning plurality and ambiguity in pragmatics.

⁶⁷In an effort to test how well speech acts can be identified and processed *en masse*, Martin Weisser states: "Any type of linguistic annotation is a highly complex and interpretive process, but none more so than pragmatic annotation [...] [This is because one] always needs to take into account levels above the individual word and may even need to refer to contextual information beyond those textual units" [202, p. 84]

independent meaning is inferred and perpetuated by the grammatical structures of the language used [203]. However, there are several ways to understanding grammar. One approach coming from the so-called usage-based tradition is construction grammar as per Adele Goldberg [204], [205], which emphasizes that (linguistic) meaning is more dynamically spread across language sequences than just fixed words or sentences, and that traditional semiotic systems do not suffice in reflecting cognitive realities [206, pp. 54-55], [207], [208, pp. 50-52], [209].⁶⁸

For the purpose of this thesis, I join in with the usage-based tradition. However, I primarily examine the most perceptible component of **FL** patterns, i.e., the text's surface, which incidentally corresponds with semantics and other linguistic aspects. Sarah Brommer proposes the same [216, p. 57]: she distinguishes 'patterns' (*Muster*) from other **FL** forms by defining that they only refer to a text's surface elements without compelling any semantics.

Next, I discuss how other types of **FL** are defined and used in linguistics, followed by research traditions concerning their flexibility as well as their embedding into larger structures, or as I deem it, environments.

2.2.3. Formulaicity: Linguistic Perspectives

2.2.3.1. Language Patterns

The amount of linguistic work that has dealt with (expressions of) formulaicity especially over the last 40 years is overwhelming, with some of the most formative works stemming from John Sinclair⁶⁹ [217], Alison Wray [218], and Norbert Schmitt [219].⁷⁰

By the 2000s, linguists have found over 40 different terms to refer to **FL** patterns, and besides being somehow conventionalized, they practically all designate repetitive language [218]. Some of the most important ones are "collocations, idioms, lexical phrases, lexical bundles, metaphors, proverbs, phrasal verbs, *n*-grams, conc-grams, and com-

⁶⁸Construction grammar is referred here for a specific reason. David Wood remarks that **FL** patterns can be linked to language models that prioritize "levels of structure related to speech act realizations" [210, p. 10]. Since constructions are originally understood as "conventionalised pairings of form and function" [205, p. 1], I derive that formulas can be deemed constructions. More specifically, Ewa Dąbrowska claims that constructions "emerge from formulas" [211, p. 87]. Support for these interpretations is ample [212, p. 4], [213, p. 182]. See [214], [215] for a more critical deconstruction of construction grammar at the semantics-pragmatics interface.

⁶⁹Notably, I find idiomacy and open choice as per his work to be analogous to formulaicity and flexibility.

⁷⁰Linguistic research into formulaicity goes back much further, at least into the 1920s, and subsequently left its mark in a wide array of fields, e.g., literary studies, anthropology, philosophy, sociology, psychology and neurology [210, ch. 1]

pounds" [220, p. 31]. Most of this terminology is still used across a variety of areas, the most prominent 'strands' being Cognitive Linguistics and Psycholinguistics⁷¹, Language Learning and Language Acquisition, as well as Corpus Linguistics and Computational Linguistics. What all **FL** terms seem to have in common is that they represent a sequence that consists of more than one word, is conventionalized, and carries a novel meaning. 'Conventionalized' means that the sequence is conceptually stored, retrieved, and used like a single word; a meaning being 'novel' requires it to symbolically refer to something that semantically surpasses its constituents [210, p. 2]. Two aspects in which these sequences differ are compositionality, i.e., the relation between their semantic sum and its summands, and productivity, i.e., their potential in being meaningfully extended [220, p. 32]. Notably, these features are differently pronounced across **FL** variants.

To differentiate **FL** terminology, David Wood has undertaken a comprehensive classification [224, pp. 31-35], which is practically equivalent to a more recent one by Susan Hunston [225, p. 140]. According to them, one can distinguish sequences by

1. structural, semantic, or syntactic properties (e.g., collocations, idioms)
2. pragmatic utility (e.g., lexical phrases, pragmatic formulas)
3. corpora distribution (e.g., lexical bundles, conc-grams)

Judging from their description, lexical bundles are practically equivalent to n -grams, i.e., any sequence of n words, which do not necessarily has to represent a single unit of meaning. Pragmatic formulas refer to 'situation-bound utterances'; they represent "social formulas used by speech communities in the realization of pragmatics" [226, p. 207]. For the purpose of this thesis, my preferred definition of a formula finds itself somewhere between these two classes.

Another useful vantage point in understanding formulas as sequences is provided in the works of Noah Bubenhofer. He declares patterns of language use (*Sprachgebrauchsmuster*) [227, p. 43] that are a result specifically of pragmatic communication. His definition also entails that a **FL** pattern serves as a template that is later (partly) reproduced to create new strings (*Zeichenkomplexe*) [227, p. 23], which notably coincides with how diplomatists conceptualize how formulas can be used. Sarah Brommer [216, p. 54] extends this view by other criteria, one of which is significance, i.e., either statistical or contextual. Her definition of **FL** puts patterns at the center, i.e., a set of recurring words or phrases that are significant and typical for a given linguistic context.

⁷¹Here, formulaicity is heavily intertwined with predictability [221], [222]. Véronique Verhagen et al. [223] argue that, in terms of language processing, one becomes better at predicting **FL** typical of a particular register by becoming more experienced with it.

Based on respective properties, they are considered exemplary in both the sense of a template and a model. Patterns can be concrete and observable, as well as abstract and conceptual [216, p. 56].

To better pinpoint variation in **FL** sequences, Noah Bubenhofer [227, p. 117] identified factors that influence their dispersion.⁷² Generalizing them results in these parameters:

- Length: how long are sequences (e.g., what is the size of n for n -grams?)
- Span: are sequences continuous (e.g., are skip-grams employed?)
- Boundary: are sequences limited (e.g., by clause, sentence, or paragraph?)
- Grouping: are sequences grouped (e.g., by order⁷³, lemmatization, normalization?)
- Supervision: in which mode are sequences identified (e.g., generated or searched?)

Highlighting the aspect of supervision, it appears that there are two main directions in which an investigation of formulaic flexibility goes. They are in an opposition based on how an analysis is fundamentally set up. The first way is to actively search for previously known manifestations of **FL**, e.g., by listing concordances of established idiomatic expressions. The second is more passive, whereby **FL** is allowed to accumulate 'naturally', which is facilitated by computational means, e.g., by data-driven analyses.

Notably, both modes require a corpus, i.e., a representation of language in the form of many texts.⁷⁴ How such a corpus is built depends on the answer to following question: where should the investigation on formulaicity commence? Linguists have come up with many starting points, to which I here refer to as analytical contexts.⁷⁵ For some, the primary context is represented by the linguistic quality of a **FL** sequence (e.g., morphology or grammar). For others, these are only secondary, with the primary context being the type or size of the corpus to which such a sequence is compared.⁷⁶ Especially the latter contexts I refer to as environments.

2.2.3.2. Formulaic Environments

In Susan Hunston's description of phraseology [230, p. 5], formulaic environments are regarded as the space where one would encounter or expect a **FL** sequence. Apart

⁷²While these factors are based on corpora of written language, they can certainly be adapted to cater for oral language.

⁷³Lukas Michelbacher et al. [228] refer to this as asymmetry.

⁷⁴See Subsection 2.3.1 on the philosophy of working with language corpora.

⁷⁵Analytical contexts can be freely combined; they are not mutually exclusive.

⁷⁶While not the same, this distinction is similar to microscopic vs. macroscopic analyses in the tradition of Douglas Biber [229].

from text types, two categories of environment that linguistics has widely dealt with are register and genre. Both concern the study of language use in texts to understand characteristics and conventions of different text types. While similar, the register perspective is extraordinary as it puts the main focus on situation-dependent adaption of linguistic features to cater situational needs of a text, whereas genre only secondarily acknowledges this function [231, p. 2].⁷⁷

More than 30 years ago, ground-breaking work on the distribution of language patterns across registers was published by Douglas Biber [229]. Using factor analysis, he attributed linguistic features to meaningful bundles with functional characteristics and calculated how they vary across texts. A single text can thus be described and compared to others across various dimensions, hence the name Multi-Dimensional Analysis (MDA).⁷⁸ Despite being controversial among the linguistic community, the fundamental notions of MDA are leading to novel studies on register still today. For instance, it inspired a recent work which, by employing text similarity measures, found that register and respective linguistic features generalize consistently across dozens of languages [234].⁷⁹ Such quantitative "register-functional approaches" [237] are a prime example of how linguists have come up with individual ways of modelling FL patterns.

A more specific environment is that of legal language. It is also deemed a "sublanguage" [238, p. 316] that covers a wide range of legal discourse, both written and spoken.⁸⁰ Apart from extensive pragmatic language use, a considerable amount of repetitive language has been identified across types of legal discourse of the last 50 years. Such repetition has been especially found to reflect in functional constructions, such as in 'moves', 'arguments', or 'semantic sequences' [239]. Stanisław Goźdź-Roszkowski remarks that legal language further varies depending on legal contexts; he summarizes:

Legal genres can be described and differentiated in terms of their preferred phraseologies. These phraseological preferences correlate strongly with the different communicative priorities and epistemological precepts of the legal genres. Legal genres seem to be characterized by a varying degree of formulaicity [239, p. 1524].

Based on this understanding, the actual realizations of FL are mainly determined by a

⁷⁷Admittedly, the boundaries between the two are not easily separable, even more so since they share approaches with discourse analysis [232].

⁷⁸MDA was extended by clustering algorithms soon after, arriving at text types based on register [233].

⁷⁹See for instance also [235], [236].

⁸⁰Apart from register and genre studies, other notable fields that are tightly connected with legal discourse are legal and forensic linguistics.

language community's rules and expectations of how a communication should unfold. Furthermore, it can be deduced that the use of such patterns varies significantly between larger environments, e.g., different text genres, but also noticeably within them, e.g., legal texts. These observations for contemporary legal texts clearly reinforce my expectations of historical legal texts to similarly contain **FL**.

Summing up, there is an abundance of linguistic definitions and approaches to formulaicity. This is explained by the many backgrounds against which **FL** has been investigated. Moreover, linguists have come up with several ways to anticipate formulaic flexibility. While they found many ways to conceptualize and scrutinize individual **FL** patterns, linguists have also looked at how it manifests in larger contexts. It is apparent that, to a varying degree, the frequency of language patterns as well as how it interrelates with their distributions, hence its meaning, plays a major role in determining their formulaicity.

To make generalizations of text and about language more feasible, it is essential to do so in a most systematic manner, i.e., in a way that allows for reliably observing prevalent or underlying rules. For this, linguists have increasingly resorted to processing large quantities of language data.

2.3. Computational Linguistics

Computational linguists mainly work with corpora, i.e., large (electronic) collections of text. To tie in with the previous chapter, a major aspect of research into **FL** has shown to be supervision mode. In this context, one distinguishes between corpus-based and corpus-driven approaches. The former concerns linguistic rules governing language structures (top-down); in the latter, rules are derived from word patterns (bottom-up) [240]. Arguably, the majority of linguistic studies employing corpora have followed the corpus-based paradigm in the past. However, there is a trend towards corpus-driven and hybrid work, accelerated by a cross-fertilization of disciplines and attempts to handle text as data. The present thesis continues in this tradition.

2.3.1. Corpora

Word frequency lists have been investigated before the 19th century, but only from the 1960s onward has working with actual corpora become more mainstream, with research centers emerging by the 1970s that were dedicated to doing 'linguistics with a corpus' [241]. Corresponding to above approaches, a corpus allows for observing *or* deriving

language patterns. The main premise to using a corpus is that, to gain representative knowledge about a set of material, many subset observations are better than single ones [242, pp. 2-3]. Arguably, this aspect of representativeness is not limited to language, but is extended to how it relates to reality, i.e., what is being performed and achieved with language. This is in line with observations made by Tony McEnery and Vaclav Brezina, who state that "a corpus represents an amalgam of social and physical interactions" [213, p. 114]. In the words of Jessy Egbert:

[A corpus is] a proxy for a language domain of interest, with the hope that we can glean from the corpus generalizable insights about language use in that domain. [243, p. 5]

Since this approach is fundamentally empirical, questions about and assumptions of internal language systems are not necessarily their prime concern; they only arise when interpreting results [244, p. 175]. In fact, corpora can accommodate any theoretical perspective [213, p. 49]. Doing linguistics with a corpus makes it possible to determine which elements of a language are subject to certain regularities; the difference to classical linguistics here is the fact that the analysis as well as the evaluation are carried out as mathematically or quantitatively as possible. As such, one desired result are probabilities according to which linguistic phenomena occur in the examined corpus [245].⁸¹

2.3.2. Processing Tasks

Before examining a corpus, it is good practice to formulate research questions. Often, these are formalized only to a certain extent, and for them to be measurable and their answers comparable, they require a meticulous interpretation. To make this interpretative process more compartmentalized and objective, understanding and processing text as data has become more and more algorithmic over the last decades. As such, research into language has seen a trend of being broken down into tasks. This development has coincided with corpora increasingly serving so-called real-world applications, and doing a quantitative procedure on language data in the form of a "computational linguistics task" [248, p. 2] is practice for more than 40 years now.

⁸¹Using advanced statistics in processing language data and reporting on them has been *en vogue* in language research for quite some time. One example is found in the journal *English Language and Linguistics*, in which the proportion of articles including statistical calculations in their analysis has increased from about 25 % to over 70 % within the last 25 years; qualitative research articles showed the equivalent negative trend [246, p. 1212]. Related to this, see [247] on the (statistical) replication crises in linguistics.

The development from research questions towards processing tasks has caused the latter to become highly routinized. Moreover, tasks have further branched out and become more nuanced, much owed to the workings of industries that deal with what can be called big data. Today, the web presence of Hugging Face, a company and community known for being a collection basin of Machine Learning (ML) research, divides Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks into specific categories, some of the most crucial being text classification, summarization, and generation. Each category can serve specific needs, which are not limited to linguistic research.

Understanding a linguistic research problem as a task helps not only to deconstruct the problem, but also to model and approach it in a certain way. Following the traditions of specific tasks, one can also draw on how other researchers have approached an issue before. In reference to pragmatics I reported that examining text regarding performative language is highly complex and multi-layered. To tackle this complexity, linguistic annotation can be understood as a multi-layer sequence labelling task, in which meaningful or correct labels are attached to sequences, resulting in a classification. This has especially been shown to be successful when applying Deep Learning (DL) methods [249]. In this specific example, the task and its tools do not only improve the results, but they enable it, rendering the process feasible.

Processing tasks are not limited to the use in one domain. Quite the contrary, they embody methods that can be applied across disciplines. Despite the advantages, applying models and methods from one domain to another can be highly controversial. This concern has also been found with regards to the relation between linguistics and NLP. Reinhard Köhler and Arjuna Tuzzi summarize it as follows:

Researchers which are interested in quantitative text analysis but without much linguistic background tend to use methods and measures they are familiar with, e.g. from information theory, mechanics, statistics or quantum physics. These methods may sometimes work for practical purposes even if one cannot be sure whether they really represent the properties the researcher aims at. However, very often, they are inappropriate when applied to language and make unrealistic assumptions: infinite length of texts, infinite size of lexicons, normal distribution of the data etc. Moreover, they are rarely interpretable in linguistic terms. For a linguistically meaningful and valid analysis of linguistic objects, linguistic models are required [250, p. 111].⁸²

⁸²See [119] for an early anticipation of possibly erroneous assumptions in language data, and [251] for a more recent one.

From this description, two points appear to be especially important. First, not every method is suited for every language data. Second, methodology should serve linguistics, not the other way around. This requires researchers to make clear declarations on what the employment of a method should achieve and to which extent findings can be generalized. Furthermore, it can be surmised that scholars should be highly attentive to using correct terminology. Applying methods across disciplines must anticipate different research paradigms and naming conventions. In the instance of this thesis, tackling the variety of **FL** with processing tasks first requires a terminological disambiguation [252, p. 2], resulting in a clear-cut definition of the research subject.

Language processing tasks have become an integral part of how methodology is discussed and negotiated in the fields of **NLP** and **ML**. Almost all of them rely on the assumption that language can be predicted to some degree. This is also true for the investigation of Formulaic Language (**FL**), which requires a certain modeling of language depending on the formalities of the task. Upcoming, I outline the inner workings of some example models.

2.3.3. Formulaicity: Computational Perspectives

2.3.3.1. Language Models

To make language data more actionable, researchers have come up with different ways of understanding text and through a Language Model (**LM**), i.e., expressing language numerically [253, p. 32]. All of them thrive through some form of calculating frequencies and distribution probabilities of language patterns in a given corpus. This highlights the importance of the underlying data, as it determines how a model represents a given language.

There are several forms and 'levels' of **LM** as they differ in their complexity. A simple type are n -gram models that are based on transition probabilities derived from sets with n length. In essence, they have been pioneered more than a century ago by Andrei Markov, and taken up later by Claude Shannon. After receiving a heavy backlash from Noam Chomsky and the rationalist camp of linguistics in the 1960s, probability models have returned to the stage only in the 1970s [253, p. 55].⁸³ Based on these, linguists have investigated **FL** as formalized finite-state automata, and their flexibility described by probabilities as Markov chains. By the 1990s, such micro-structural rules have been

⁸³Formative works on text as data in this period were produced by Zellig Harris [254], William Woods [255], and Maurice Gross [256].

conceptualized as collocational frameworks by Antoinette Renouf and John Sinclair [257], and as local grammars by Maurice Gross [258]. Their essence was later taken up in the development of colostruational analysis. Both collocations and colostruactions continue to be relevant for FL research to this day.

More sophisticated LM understand language in more continuous space. Expressing distributions of sequences across texts as tensors not only better captures their structure, but it also enables inference of their semantic similarity [253, p. 56]. The inner workings of these latent distributions — similarity in significance through word co-occurrence — have already been identified around 1950 and made increasingly tangible in the following 20 years, such as by Gerard Salton [253, pp. 107-109]. However, their full potential of representing a language was only unlocked as dense vectors, e.g., word embeddings. Their advent in the 2010s has finally met the call of scholars that had been "crying out for better language models" [252, p. 1], with some of the most prominent ones being word2vec [259], GloVe [260], and fasttext [261].⁸⁴

Sparse vector models vary greatly from dense ones with regard to how efficient they learn a word's contextual information and how well they generalize to new context. Also in these two points, static vector models, e.g., word embeddings, differ considerably from dynamic ones, e.g., transformers. More specifically, the former have fixed context windows, the latter allow selectively focusing on different parts of the input sequence at each step of the computation, which is called self-attention [253, p. 212].⁸⁵

The cherry on top of previous neural network implementations are bi-directional transformers. They are pre-trained on large amounts of data, e.g., using a Masked Language Model (MLM) of some complexity, and can be fine-tuned via transfer learning to anticipate more contextualized embeddings [253, p. 228]. The most famous implementation is called Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) [264], which has been extensively used and specified, e.g., as a reduced DistilBERT [265] or the multilingual XLM-RoBERTa [266].

The implementation and evaluation of advanced LM requires thorough methodological reflection. While simple n -gram language models can be evaluated using perplexity measures, advanced models are often tested against validation sets or by using them in specific applications [253, p. 55]. Their implementation can thus be judged by means of statistical tests or performance metrics of processing tasks [253, pp. 69-72], with a

⁸⁴Word embeddings have been also applied to historical data quickly after [262].

⁸⁵The notion of attention is a driving factor in the success of today's state-of-the-art language models. As per the transformer model's authors Ashish Vaswani et al.: "Attention is all you need" [263].

majority of studies employing test accuracy measures, such as precision, recall, and F-scores [267, p. 1385]. Questioning these measures as to what they mean and entail is an integral part of such applications.

To understand **LM** in the context formulaicity, it is helpful to investigate specific tasks they are designed to serve and how their performance is measured. One task that has been key in advancing **NLP** is sequence prediction. For instance, causal language modeling predicts the likelihood of the next word given only the preceding words, while bi-directional models exploit adjacency in both directions. Their fundamental reliance on co-occurrences implies that **LM** inherently thrive with formulaicity. As such, models 'learn' structures [268, p. 69] from input datapoints and internalize their variability — layer by layer [269]. This reflects in their success in managing distributional semantics in processing tasks, and by quantifying the likeliness of options in sequence prediction, **LM** capture formulaic flexibility as well.⁸⁶

2.4. Synthesis

This chapter has presented three different perspectives on formulaicity, highlighting some noteworthy similarities and differences. While each discipline conceptualizes formulaicity and formulaic flexibility in its own way, there are commonalities and differences that are worth noting.⁸⁷

One of the most significant differences between disciplines is their reference value for frequency and recurrence. Diplomatists mostly focus on the diplomatic form and its correspondence to segments of **FL**, while linguists favor other differentiable linguistic units, such as sentences and texts, or larger environments, such as text types, registers, and genres. Despite this difference, both diplomatics and linguistics recognize the importance of frequency and recurrence in language, and perceive formulaicity as heavily driven by communicative conventions. Diplomatists view formulaicity in terms of legal and cultural conventions, where respective patterns are expected to appear only in certain parts of a charter. Linguistic findings support this view by stressing the importance

⁸⁶François Chollet stresses that, due to modern architectures, a **LM** can embody more than that, namely a database and program store that combines and interpolates predictions [270], which, I argue, is significantly more than just "stochastic parrots" [271].

⁸⁷Admittedly, a major reason for similarities in this context is that these disciplines have been mutually influential in their theories and methodologies. This is exemplified in the philological and pragmatic traces left in diplomatic literature, or vice versa, the scrutiny of charter texts across Medieval and language studies. Another obvious reason is that linguistics is *the* science to describe text, and its approaches are encompassing enough to describe arguably anything that is written.

of regularized patterns in communication. For the given context, this suggests that high frequency of formulas per se is not necessarily a qualifying condition for a charter to be considered formulaic; the contextual quality of a formula and its validation by scribes and scholars are to be considered equally important.

With regards to computational approaches, it is evident that they can support both diplomatic and linguistic perspectives on formulaicity. By using large data sets, one can identify patterns and quantify the likelihood of formulas appearing in certain environments, making **FL** visible. This entails expressing text as data that is mathematically more tangible. Additionally, **LM** can infer (pragmatic) meaning through accumulated co-occurrence. This means that quantitative methods can not only highlight **FL** of high recurrence, but also narrow down their meaning.⁸⁸

Having discussed similarities and differences in the views on formulaicity across disciplines, thereby answering **RQ1**, I now progress to describing the scope of my analysis.

⁸⁸While the great potential of such research is especially reflected in the rising capabilities of **AI**-fuelled language models, there lies also great danger in neglecting linguistically accrued knowledge that is less readily expressed through numbers. Since the 1990s, increased efforts are made to counter the purely stochastic finding of repetitive sequences [272]. As such, more linguistically-driven units of analysis are represented by phrases or chunks, with the former formed by syntactically fully valid sequences, the latter only partly so. Processing data for identifying such sequences comes in the form of (shallow) parsing, which has also been attempted for **MHG** [273], where conventions of proper syntax had not yet been established, and phrasemes just commence to increasingly regularize [274]. On another note: For specific language processing task, vector-based language models can also be improved by positionally incorporating linguistic dependencies [275], [276]. See also [271], [277] for some recent discussion points.

Part II.

Analysis and Results

3. Data and Method

This chapter describes the scope of my analysis. All data and code is provided in a dedicated GitHub repository.⁸⁹ It includes Python implementations in functional Jupyter notebooks as well as instructions on setting up the environment. Each notebook is dedicated to answering a specific research question. They are numbered accordingly. Those that only serve the preparation of the analysis are marked as another category.⁹⁰ All graphics are created by myself except noted otherwise.

3.1. Selection

The charter corpus is derived from the data behind Monasterium.⁹¹ It is strongly heterogeneous regarding its content [278, p. 248]. I emphasize that only MHG charters are examined; the results are thus limited to this specific language variety. Assumptions and claims made about charters therefore primarily concern those. With regards to the representativity of the corpora, I make a concerted effort to adhere to best-practices both within the target domain and beyond, as discussed in [20]. Even though there exists no official classification of charter types, it can be said that the large majority of the data is formed by private charters. While charters in the narrow sense can be rather diverse [279], [280] and their repositories encompass a variety of legal texts, I still treat the data as a homogeneous corpus that is representative enough for the purpose of my investigation.⁹² Notably, to situate formulaicity in charters, it is necessary to comprehensively compare it to other text categories. As a reference corpus, I use the ReM.⁹³

⁸⁹<https://github.com/atzenhofer/ma-thesis-dh-code>.

⁹⁰It is highly encouraged to examine the notebooks and their results in addition to this text.

⁹¹<https://www.monasterium.net/mom/home>.

⁹²The fact that its problematic to treat charter collections as a coherent mass of documents is reflected in the goals of a current long-term project led by Philippe Depreux, which is to conceptually disentangle the mix of Medieval formulae, litterae, and chartae: <https://www.formulae.uni-hamburg.de/>.

⁹³Another reference corpus taken into consideration is the MHGCDB, whose main purpose is, however, less linguistic than the ReM, which is visible with regards to encoding and annotating standards.

3.2. Transformation

To allow for the analysis, both corpora, i.e., Monasterium.net’s **MHG** charter subset and the reference corpus based on the **ReM**, are transformed to a unified JavaScript Object Notation (**JSON**) serialization. The main corpus is originally stored in Charters Encoding Initiative (**CEI**) Extensible Markup Language (**XML**), i.e., a dialect of the Text Encoding Initiative (**TEI**)-P4 guidelines [278]. This transformation flow from **CEI-XML** to **JSON** is omitted here, given a condensed version of the original data is provided to me only through the **DiDip** project. Notably, the transformed main corpus is annotation-free, i.e., without markup insertions, expansions, or additions.⁹⁴ This allows me to adhere more closely to the original content of the documents.

The transformation of the reference corpus is documented in a dedicated notebook.⁹⁵ One takeaway is that I prioritize already simplified and standardized versions of the reference texts, given that they better align with how I expect the main corpus to be.⁹⁶ Further, I manually translate and map the text categories to a small but meaningful set.

3.3. Pre-Processing

The preparation of the main corpus is documented in a dedicated notebook as well.⁹⁷ This entails dropping duplicates, aligning date values, detecting languages, and filtering by date and language. For charters to qualify date-wise, I set the lower and upper bound at 1100 and 1400 CE, respectively.⁹⁸

After detecting and differentiating between historical languages with a model developed in **DiDip**⁹⁹, a further distinction of false-positively detected German charters is done. While sometimes, the initial model is reliable in detecting non-Germanic text, it fails for others due to its architecture, given that it is limited by truncation and hence more useful for shorter sequences of text. Therefore, I use the library **langid** [281] on top to detect Latin sequences. By the library’s probability normalization, the texts of the

⁹⁴Leftover annotations without **XML** tags are carefully removed.

⁹⁵<https://github.com/atzenhofer/ma-thesis-dh-code/blob/master/py/0a-transform-reference.ipynb>.

⁹⁶Data in Monasterium.net primarily serves diplomatists, not historical linguists, which is one reason why its text data has the tendency to be normalized.

⁹⁷<https://github.com/atzenhofer/ma-thesis-dh-code/blob/master/py/0b-preprocessing-main.ipynb>.

⁹⁸Comparing this cutoff with periodizations compiled by Thorsten Roelcke [4], the lower bound might in fact even be deemed too early. Only a few charters from before 1250 have survived to the present day. Towards the end of the 13th century, the amount slowly increases: around 1350, the transition from Latin to German charters allegedly peaks [138, pp. 96-97].

⁹⁹<https://huggingface.co/ERCDiDip/langdetect>.

resulting corpus are classified as **MHG** with a confidence score of over 95 %. I surmise the rest to be widely due to Latin phrases and formulas that can barely be separated from German charter language of this time. At this point, the main corpus consists of around 9,300 charters.

For a meaningful comparison, I align both corpora based on the character level, given that they vary within and between them. These steps are documented in a dedicated notebook.¹⁰⁰ The main goal is to have the same or a highly similar character set; I do not aim at having a single perfect encoding of all texts, but one that is systematic, clean, and that enables a transparent analysis. As such, I implement a number of normalization and mapping procedures that are built on how scholars have recently attempted [282], [283, ch. 5] to simplify **MHG**. In principle, I quantify character sets and compare their usage selectively. Depending on how individual characters manifest, this either results in a text being disregarded completely or to be normalized. After an initial manual correction, I add an automatic cleaning procedure using the Python library `cleantext` as a finishing touch.

The effect of this standardization process on the number of charters is visualized in Figure 3.1. The histogram with 15 bins shows the distribution of charters across years for the full and the reduced set. Interestingly, the progression in time coincides with charters being more affected by the pre-processing steps. In sum, about 2,000 charters were deducted from the pre-processed set.

Figure 3.1.: Pre-processed vs. processed charter counts by binned years.

¹⁰⁰<https://github.com/atzenhofer/ma-thesis-dh-code/blob/master/py/0c-preprocessing-norm.ipynb>.

The result is thus transformed into a merged table and exported to one full version and one without punctuation. As such, the main corpus is formed by roughly 7,000 charters.

3.4. Algorithmic Description

Formulaicity: Before exploring **FL** in charters, a major task lies in pinning down charters as a distinct text type or category that is ought to be different from others with regards to formulaicity.¹⁰¹ To accomplish this, I employ three different sets of measures.¹⁰² The first set consists of five **LD** indices, where diversity can be understood as an opposite to formulaicity. These are computed by using the library `lexicalrichness` [285]. From a total of five indices, two are simple measures, i.e., Root Type-Token Ratio (**RTTR**) [286], [287] and Dugast’s Uber index [288].

$$\text{rttr} = \frac{t}{\sqrt{w}} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\text{Dugast} = \frac{\log(w)^2}{\log(w) - \log(t)} \quad (3.2)$$

In both equations, t is a text’s number of total unique words (types) and w the total number of words (tokens). For 3.1, the result is a ratio that indicates the average number of times each word is used; for 3.2, the result is a logarithmic ratio. Adding to these, I take three indices that are the result of specific algorithms:

- Moving Average Type-Token Ratio (**MATTR**): the average **TTRs** over successive segments of a text, i.e., rolling windows, then takes their total average [289].
- Measure of Textual Lexical Diversity (**MTLD**): the mean length of sequential words of a text above a certain **TTR** threshold score, iterates over words down to threshold, then increases factor counter and commences with new segment [92]).
- Hypergeometric Distribution Diversity (**HDD**): the probability of getting at least one occurrence of a unique word in a text, based on a random draw of a given size; the index sums up contributions of all unique words, i.e., the product of the probability and the multiplicative inverse of the sample size [290] [91, p. 460].¹⁰³

This selection is made because these indices represent categories that are unique in what

¹⁰¹<https://github.com/atzenhofer/ma-thesis-dh-code/blob/master/py/2-formulaicity.ipynb>.

¹⁰²See [284] on the benefits of such comparisons.

¹⁰³Notably, a lower **HDD** means higher **LD** [91, p. 460]. This is true for Dugast’s as well.

they capture in relation to LD [290, p. 381], and they do so successfully [291]. Others are disregarded due to redundancy. For instance, Dugast’s and Maas’s are practically identical [94, p. 328]; also voc-D and HDD are highly similar [290, p. 381], and vanilla TTR is largely unsuitable for capturing LD [94].

I then contrast these with a second set, namely compression rates. These are based on methods that seek out and exploit re-occurring bit sequences in strings. I resort to three modules from the Python standard library that represent different data compression algorithms.¹⁰⁴ They are all lossless: LZMA uses the Lempel-Ziv-Markov chain algorithm, GZIP a combination of the Lempel-Ziv and Huffman coding based on shortest expected length [292, p. 118], and BZ2 the Burrows-Wheeler transform.

As a third set of measures, I calculate n -gram coverage¹⁰⁵ scores within texts and across text categories. Coverage is calculated by dividing the number of pre-identified top n -grams in a text by the total number of n -grams. The higher the coverage, the more frequently the sequences appear, structurally rendering the text more formulaic.

I thus correlate these sets, assess their trajectories over time, and critically reflect on the results. To increase the validity of my findings, I account for the variance in the number and length of texts, as well as their lexical distributions, given that they are crucial in analyzing the lexical diversity of language. I use these result to answer RQ2.

Formulas: The second task lies in identifying highly frequent FL sequences in various data-driven ways and to compare and evaluate the results in terms of capturing and quantifying (variation in) FL.¹⁰⁶ For this, I compute different string sequence constellations by equipping n -gram search with custom functionalities, i.e., association scores and skips.¹⁰⁷ To achieve this, I fundamentally resort to libraries that are widely established in NLP, e.g., nltk [295], scikit-learn, [296] and SciPy, and extend them by specific needs.

¹⁰⁴When compressing data, shorter descriptions substitute most common outcomes of a data source, while longer descriptions do so for less frequent ones [292, p. 103]. This can be understood as a more fine-grained alternative to vocabulary growth curves [293]. Notably, compression has different meanings across disciplines. In linguistics, it can refer to the fixedness of (lexico-grammatical) patterns that also manifests cognitively and influence language change [294].

¹⁰⁵Inspired by Richard Forsyth’s Python program `formulib` [112, p. 33]:
<http://www.richardsandesforsyth.net/software.html>.

¹⁰⁶<https://github.com/atzenhofer/ma-thesis-dh-code/blob/master/py/3-formulas.ipynb>.

¹⁰⁷I disregard the implementation of a (greedy or dynamic) merger. There are two main reasons for this. Firstly, a merging algorithm can result in formulas that still pose considerable redundancy. Secondly, skip-grams are more useful in the given context since they enable me to showcase and quantify flexibility of formulas in a more comprehensive way.

To apply these sequences in a more concrete task other than findings **FL**, I exploit said identification techniques to look at how top formulas vary in their distributions across or flexibility relating to charter sections. Results of this are used to answer **RQ3** and **RQ4**, which bridges the gap to the last part.

Flexibility: A third task lies in rendering visible how **FL** can vary.¹⁰⁸ For this, skipgrams are re-used to calculate the likelihood of formulas to alternate within a limited sequence. I also show how variation of formulaicity can be understood as a string similarity measuring task. As such, the structurally nearest candidates of a pre-defined sequence are determined based on a specific measure. Furthermore, to quantify the flexibility of formulas with a **LM**, I formulate the identification of co-occurrences as a sequence prediction task. For this, I fine-tune two different **PyTorch**-based models on **MHG** charter language using **transformers**: first, a minimal **DistilRoBERTa**, second, a more complex **XLM-RoBERTa**.¹⁰⁹ Finally, I use these models to identify slot-filling candidates and to perform a practical text imputation task. The prediction scores are qualitatively assessed to evaluate the performance of the model

For these tasks, I do not remove so-called stop words, given that this would be detrimental to my research goals. Also, as usual in language processing, and definitely desirable for my research goals, texts are almost always lowered, i.e., no capital letters. For taking formulaicity measures, I primarily use a data set version without punctuation marks, i.e., pure lexis. For operations with high computational cost, the data set is limited to a sub-sample; I announce it accordingly at the respective step.

¹⁰⁸<https://github.com/atzenhofer/ma-thesis-dh-code/blob/master/py/4-flexibility.ipynb>.

¹⁰⁹Their architecture and training setup is described in the respective notebooks. Both models are publicly available for testing, training, and deployment under the given license via Hugging Face: <https://huggingface.co/atzenhofer>.

4. Analysis

4.1. Formulaicity

4.1.1. Measures

Before calculating and comparing any measures, I assess how the texts' vocabularies are distributed to anticipate possible trends in the data. For this, I take a random sample of 50 charters to approximate the other category numbers, and I calculate the total unique words, list their numbers and group per text category, as seen in Table 4.1.

Category	Number	Size
Miscellaneous	55	16,933
Legend	43	15,389
Biblical poetry	49	13,536
Epic	25	12,800
Sermon	33	11,929
Translation	22	11,526
Didactic poetry	32	10,683
Prayer	74	4,680
Charter	50	3,688
Recipe	13	3,238

Table 4.1.: Total number of texts and vocabulary sizes by text category. Sorted in descending order by vocabulary size.

Table 4.1 shows noticeable variations in the numbers and types of categories. There are several reasons for this disparity. Firstly, the variation is likely due to differences in the ability of texts to be transmitted. Secondly, text collections often contain single text items of the reference corpus, which are treated as single texts. Thirdly, text types are grouped together as larger text categories during the reference corpus transformation. In sum, these categories have different vocabulary sizes, primarily because they differ significantly in string length.

The text lengths are represented as bins in two figures: Figure 4.1a displays the full set of texts, which have a wide range of lengths and thus require a logarithmic scale to be visualized meaningfully. Meanwhile, Figure 4.1b shows all texts, but only after removing outliers that exceed 1.5 times the Interquartile Range (IQR) of text length.

Figure 4.1.: Text lengths by number of texts.

While I plot these data to show how heterogeneous the data is, I do not simultaneously remove them as candidates for the analysis. Following up, I calculate how much of the vocabulary each text category shares with each other.

Figure 4.2 indicates some vocabulary-related trends in the data. First, prayers, recipes, and charters have a relatively low share with other categories. This indicates a statistical connection between a text category's total vocabulary size, as illustrated in 4.1, and its share with others. Second, the relation between nearly all other categories shows that they share a vocabulary of at least 40 %, again with a higher individual vocabulary size being a correlate. Third, and most importantly, charters, even though they have a larger vocabulary than recipes, share a significantly low amount of this with others.

Looking at character distributions across text categories as per the respective notebook, there are visible trends of certain characters to be most present in certain categories, again most noticeably in charters. I affirm this by assessing both the full data set as well as one where charters are sampled. Besides that given charters have a low vocabulary size, I surmise that these differences arise from previous normalization processes since, arguably, diplomatists have different conventions to standardize a text than historical

Figure 4.2.: Heat map of categorical vocabulary share in percentages. Rounded to the nearest whole percentage point.

linguists do.¹¹⁰ In addition, the character alignment I apply to the main corpus is minimally different from the reference, which can account for a slight skew in the data.

Advancing towards the actual calculation of formulaicity measures, I implement a lower threshold regarding tokens, i.e., total word counts, as suggested by the literature [92, p. 8], [297, p. 554]. This procedure affects text categories unequally. The most significant decrease is found in the prayers, which lose more than half their items. Other categories are only similarly affected when compared by percentages; the absolute numbers are relatively stable. The effect on charters is effectively null since I re-sample them after setting the threshold.

4.1.1.1. Lexical Diversity

Finally, I calculate **LD** indices as described in Chapter 3 for every text. To anticipate any trends in categories' scores, I compute the correlations of **LD** indices.

¹¹⁰Perhaps even more worth mentioning: charters often contain abbreviations in their originals, given that their scribes were accustomed to saving time and space. The rate at which diplomatists expand these in transcriptions — with or without specifically encoded mark-up — is unknown. In any case, it definitely plays a role in taking this text category's measures.

Figure 4.3.: Correlation heat map of **LD** indices. Rounded to two decimal points

The resulting correlation heat map in Figure 4.3 indicates that indices are quite different in what they capture and hence represent. There appear to be two camps of indices, where one is formed by stronger correlates, e.g., by **MATTR**, **MTLD**, and **HDD**. This underscores their consistency as suggested by the literature. The second is formed by the other two indices whose correlation-ratios are considerably below the first. It is obvious that especially **RTTR** poses an inconsistent and overall rather low correlation. Notably, there are no negative correlations. Against this backdrop, the mean **LD** measures for each category are calculated and displayed in Table 4.2.

Category	RTTR	MATTR	MTLD	HDD	Dugast
Biblical poetry	14.87	0.89	104.55	0.87	57.28
Charter	9.88	0.88	91.18	0.84	54.46
Didactic poetry	15.02	0.87	88.43	0.86	54.01
Epic	17.05	0.90	112.91	0.88	52.46
Legend	16.10	0.90	113.04	0.88	57.61
Miscellaneous	13.60	0.85	68.03	0.83	48.43
Prayer	10.36	0.82	54.68	0.82	48.57
Recipe	10.20	0.81	46.08	0.77	44.88
Sermon	14.91	0.87	77.05	0.86	51.20
Translation	15.95	0.85	63.95	0.84	51.82

Table 4.2.: Mean **LD** indices by category. Rounded to two decimal points, with most formulaic values highlighted for each text category. Sorted alphabetically.

The overall highest lexical diversities are found in the categories of epic, legend, and biblical poetry, with excessive scores by **MATTR** and **MTLD**. Comparing the text categories by these two measures, the lowest and hence most formulaic are recipes and prayers. By taking a closer look at each measure, it becomes apparent that charters are, in fact, only average in terms of **LD**. Even more so, they are significantly more diverse than the majority of other texts by the measure of **MTLD**. Interestingly, the **RTTR** suggests that charters are relatively formulaic, with similar values posed by recipes and prayers. While **MTLD** is known to be relatively consistent across text sizes, the **RTTR** is highly prone to be skewed by such variance. To investigate this further, I take a look at the textual measures of my data set. For this, the mean lengths, tokens, and types are computed for each category and displayed accordingly in Table 4.3.

Category	Length	Tokens	Types
Epic	45,133	8,388	1,501
Translation	38,722	6,979	1,323
Miscellaneous	31,552	5,713	1,016
Legend	28,295	5,206	1,124
Sermon	28,008	5,075	1,030
Didactic poetry	25,163	4,622	1,002
Biblical poetry	21,377	3,952	885
Recipe	11,945	2,234	452
Prayer	5,606	990	321
Charter	2,435	416	200

Table 4.3.: Mean textual measures by text category. Sorted in descending order by mean text length.

This computation reveals that text categories are extremely diverse in terms of mean length, types, and tokens. Besides prayers, charters are the shortest text category by far, with didactic poetry being 10 times, epics even 20 times longer. These numbers can be viewed in conjunction with vocabulary sizes displayed initially in Table 4.1. Just taking these two perspectives into account, it can be surmised that recipes and prayers are more formulaic than charters: While they pose longer mean text lengths, types, and tokens, their vocabulary sizes are relatively equal when compared to the number of texts prevalent in the data set. To better comprehend the relation between **LD** indices and text measures, the correlations between these are calculated and displayed in the heatmap of Figure 4.4.

By correlating the measures with the lexical diversity measures, it becomes obvious

Figure 4.4.: Correlation heat map of text measures and **LD** indices. Rounded to two decimal points

that **RTTR** is mostly affected by these factors. This renders the degree of formulaicity by this measure effectively invalid. The connection between **HDD** and text measures is ambiguous. More important for further analyses is statistical evidence that three **LD** indices are barely affected by different text measures, i.e., **MATTR**, **MTLD**, and Dugast's, with the latter even having a negative correlation.

In sum, charters seem to be far less formulaic than expected in terms of **LD**. However, these indices are only one type of measure that can be used to examine formulaicity in texts, and as demonstrated, they are not equally reliant in capturing the phenomenon. This is mainly because they are, to some extent, depending on different textual properties. To better pinpoint formulaicity, I continue by contrasting them with other measures.

4.1.1.2. Compression

As a next step, I calculate compression rates with different algorithms for every text in the data set. Then, their means are computed for each category. Based on these rates, it appears that charters contain the highest compression. This means that they pose high redundancy and re-occurrence on the level of bits, rendering them the most formulaic text category by this measure. Interestingly, prayers and recipes have a noticeably lower compression rate than charters, even though they have similar vocabulary sizes and **LD** scores. This suggests that high compression rate may be due to charters being shorter

in length than most other text categories. To account for this variation, I set a token limit (floor of 100; top of 1,000) for the texts. Based on this concentrated version, I re-calculate compression rates. Results are visualized in Table 4.4.

Category	GZIP	BZ2	LZMA
Legend	0.46	0.44	0.51
Biblical poetry	0.45	0.43	0.50
Didactic poetry	0.44	0.44	0.52
Recipe	0.44	0.44	0.52
Charter	0.43	0.42	0.49
Translation	0.43	0.40	0.47
Epic	0.43	0.40	0.46
Miscellaneous	0.42	0.42	0.49
Sermon	0.41	0.39	0.44
Prayer	0.40	0.40	0.46

Table 4.4.: Mean compression rate by category based on concentrated sub-set. Rounded to two decimal points. Sorted in descending order by GZIP, with most formulaic values highlighted for each text category.

As can be taken from Table 4.4, the limitation on the data causes compression rates to instantly harmonize across all categories. I explain this by the fact that charters are, on average, much shorter than most other text categories.¹¹¹ Repeating the analysis with different thresholds does not change the outcome: compression rates for charters are only mediocre. Any shifts of the top or lowest rate for other categories I explain by the variance in the number of texts that arises from setting token thresholds. For instance, by greatly narrowing down the upper limit, the category of recipes gains a significant boost in its mean compression rate. Given that I am also interested in how formulaicity measures interrelate, I next correlate text compression with lexical diversity, as visualized in the heat map of Figure 4.5. According to Figure 4.5, the LD index most correlated with text measures is also negatively correlated — strongly so — with compression, further adding to the volatility of RTTR to text length. The correlation with Dugast’s is also no surprise, given that it heavily builds on *hapax legomena* which naturally decrease the efficiency of compression algorithms. Interestingly, the indices MTLD and MATTR exhibit only a negligible correlation, which specifically bolsters the persistence of the former in being practically agnostic to text measures.

¹¹¹As demonstrated in the notebook, there is a high negative correlation between text measures and compression rates.

Figure 4.5.: Correlation heat map of compression algorithms and **LD** indices. Rounded to two decimal points.

After comparing lexical diversity and compression rates across texts, it seems that formulaicity in charters is not very pronounced. Quite the opposite: based on some measures, charters are comparably diverse in terms of bit and word sequence repetition. While charters appear relatively monotonous at the character level, they do not in larger structures.¹¹² Overall, based on previous measures, formulaicity in charters is not exceptional, and there is ample evidence that other text categories have stronger correlations with formulaicity.

4.1.1.3. Coverage

While the previous two measures focus mostly on the word level, I now calculate a score that focuses on longer sequences, making it more independent of the other formulaicity measures. For this, I calculate two coverage scores for each text¹¹³, i.e., n -gram self coverage and category coverage. The former represents the rate by which a text is

¹¹²Picking up on the initial report on character distributions, there is no clear explanation as to why charters amass certain characters that noticeably, even though they are not that repetitive on the word level. I hypothesize that there might be a connection between the word type and character distributions. For instance, charters usually contain a plethora of proper nouns and named entities; there is a good chance that the tendency of entity names to have similar leading characters skews exactly this statistic. However, I do not employ Part of Speech (**POS**) tagging in this analysis, leaving this only a guess.

¹¹³I here use the concentrated version as described in Subsection 4.1.1.1, which limits the charters to a sample of 50, and adds a token floor and top.

covered by its own top- k n -grams. The latter represents the rate by which a text is covered by its category’s top- k n -grams. Further, I compute relative scores, i.e., the relation between categorical and self coverage. This is done under the premise that a relative score could indicate that the text has unique or distinct language patterns that are not well-represented by the category’s top n -grams; the higher, the more diverse.¹¹⁴ Selected results with $n=3$, top- $k=10$ are visible in Table 4.5.¹¹⁵

Category	Category-	Self-	Relative-
Recipe	0.029	0.088	3.038
Didactic poetry	0.018	0.064	3.478
Prayer	0.014	0.078	5.707
Miscellaneous	0.011	0.096	8.719
Translation	0.009	0.036	3.981
Charter	0.007	0.055	8.176
Epic	0.007	0.026	3.806
Biblical poetry	0.007	0.037	5.033
Sermon	0.006	0.030	4.692
Legend	0.005	0.033	7.088

Table 4.5.: Mean coverage scores by text category with $n=3$, top- $k=10$. Rounded to three decimal points. Sorted in descending order by category coverage, with most formulaic values highlighted for each text category.

With a focus on charters, results in Table 4.5 show that they have a low category coverage and a medium self coverage. Accordingly, the relative coverage is high, which means that charters contain relatively diverse sequences, even though they are relatively brief. By running the analysis again with increasingly higher n , the rank of charters in terms of high category coverage and relative scores prevails. Based on coverage, charters are not particularly repetitive.

To triangulate this observation, I check whether coverage scores are influenced by text measures. I hence separately correlate self coverage and category coverage with text measures based on the concentrated sub-set. As per the notebook, it is found that correlation values between text features and category coverage is highly neutral. However,

¹¹⁴I also test whether there is a correlation between the coverage scores. In fact, the different types of coverage correlate by n , and likely also by k , but they do not across types. This means that self coverage and category coverage, while logically connected, form two separate indicators of formulaicity.

¹¹⁵Sizes of n and k are set completely intuitively. Arguably, but not evidently, given text categories share a large amount of 2-grams, but probably not 3-grams and higher, which puts a higher value on a larger n . This tendency is supported by previous research: Michael Stubbs and Isabel Barth found that FL segments can function as text-type discriminator [298].

there is a noteworthy negative correlation between self coverage and text measures. This can be causally explained since these measures are more or less directly connected: the fewer different words there are in a text, the higher is the coverage by its repetitive sequences. Summing up, category coverage turns out to be a more reliant measure than self coverage, and it is nearly agnostic to text measures as well, rendering it an indicator that is specifically interesting when compared across text categories.¹¹⁶

4.1.2. Measures Across Time

Upon further examination of the texts, it is discovered that the level of formulaicity in charters, as measured by various metrics, is only average. While these results primarily shed light on how the main corpus relates to the reference, another use of formulaicity measures is to compare them across time. This prompts me to investigate whether there are respective trends in the full set of charters. To accomplish this, I compare selected **LD** measures, i.e., **MTLD** and Dugast's as suggested in the literature and evidently consistent in the analysis of formulaicity. For compression, I only take **GZIP**, given that, as per the mean values, this algorithm poses the least amount of spread across categories. In addition, 3-gram category coverage scores are incorporated. This is done for two main reasons. Firstly, they are widely agnostic to text measures. Secondly, with regards to n , coverage is structurally not too far away from the other measure while still capturing a different aspect of formulaicity in the material.

Since the overwhelming majority of **MHG** charters in the given data set stems from the 14th century, I apply a respective cut-off. Further, to get a comprehensive picture despite variance in text lengths and numbers (per year), the data is grouped and visualized in different functions, i.e., the full set, a 10 % sub-sample, and in intervals of roughly equal sizes. In order to display these meaningfully, I employ rolling averages with fixed window sizes. These sizes are different for the full data set and the others, but they are consistent across measures. This is done to anticipate the sparsity of data that arises from the sampling procedures. Also, it helps to reduce the noise and thereby highlights the actual underlying trends.¹¹⁷ The trajectory of formulaicity is depicted in the subplots of Figure 4.6.

Based on Figure 4.6, formulaicity in charters seems to have slightly declined in the

¹¹⁶Notably, the results are most definitely skewed by the fact that the original text categories are of considerably different sizes and lengths. Computing the coverage scores without thresholds would surely influence the actual ranks.

¹¹⁷When determining these parameters, the trade-off between smoothness and accuracy of the curve is crucial.

Figure 4.6.: Formulaicity measures by years. Curves harmonized by rolling windows.

14th century. While measures seem to agree in principle, there are certain individual peculiarities to be mentioned. Most importantly, the Dugast index as well as GZIP are relatively explicit in their trend: according to these, diversity increases/compression sinks, and only minimally halts before the turning of the century. More concretely, the Dugast's drops by about 10 % and compression rates by about 5 %. The trend can be said to reflect in the coverage score as well, even though its subplot is less clear about this — mostly so, because the harmonizing procedure affects this measure differently. Notably, the actual coverage values are relatively small, arguably making this measure not that meaningful. The most ambiguous measure is clearly represented by **MTLD**. While it is in line with the development of other measures, it captures more ups and downs in the data.

Given that I have checked against several influential factors, mostly with regard to text

measures, the trends are rather stable across sets and subsets. This means that charters become less and less formulaic by the end of the 14th century, with a potential turn towards the end. While the trend is given, it is unclear how big the change really is. As such, interpretations should be made only cautiously.

To summarize this section, while charters were originally believed to be the most formulaic text category, this notion was contradicted by the results of various formulaicity measures. Additionally, examining the temporal trajectory of formulaicity in charters revealed a decrease in formulaic elements throughout the 14th century.

Although these findings received some validation through comparison to other influential factors, I emphasize that the results should be interpreted with caution. Specifically, the quality of underlying texts likely has a significant impact on the observed trends in the data, both for comparing text categories and for investigating temporal trajectories. Having established that text categories vary extraordinarily with regard to specific measures, the focus is now set completely on formulas and formulaic flexibility in charters.

4.2. Formulas

4.2.1. Formula Types

4.2.1.1. N-Grams

In order to identify **FL** patterns, I first calculate a series of top- k n -grams.¹¹⁸ Table 4.6 shows the top-10 8-grams across the whole charter data set. By comparing the individual items, it is clearly evident that plain n -grams pose a considerably high redundancy both structurally and content-wise. This is only natural since, in this form, they do not take into account any overlap between ranked candidates. Essentially, these top-10 candidates could be summarized in just three formulas, with the core represented by 'do man zalt von', 'disen brief ansehent lesent', and 'gehenkt an disen brief'.

These formulas represent sequences that are typically encountered in **MHG** charters. Also, they are recognized to have certain communicative legal functions which can be allocated to specific charter segments, as explained in Subsection 2.1.3. For instance, some are certainly part of the charter's *publicatio*, e.g., 'lesent oder horent lesen' or the *datatio*, e.g., 'brief der geben ist'. Interestingly, one core formula points to the charter's means of authentication, i.e., 'gehenkt an disen brief', which usually refers to

¹¹⁸While n -grams already play a crucial role in calculating coverage, I here assess them more qualitatively, i.e., how valuable they are in explicating formulas in terms of domain-specific functionalities.

Formula	Count
do man zalt von gottes geburt druzehenhundert jar	297
die disen brief ansehent lesent oder horent lesen	248
den die disen brief ansehent lesent oder horent	202
in dem jar do man zalt von gottes	200
dem jar do man zalt von gottes geburt	194
gehenkt an disen brief der geben ist ze	178
jar do man zalt von gottes geburt druzehenhundert	158
offenlich gehenkt an disen brief der geben ist	148
den die disen brief lesent oder horent lesen	143
allen den die disen brief lesent oder horent	142

Table 4.6.: Top-10 8-grams. Sorted in descending order by count.

the attachment of a seal. In relation to charter segments, another take-away is that the top-10 formulas found by this measure are mostly contained in the beginning or the end of charters.

While this method definitely has its advantages, i.e., relatively low computational cost while simultaneously depicting key words and phrases in a text, it is detrimental to more encompassing views on the data due to the natural redundancy it results in.

4.2.1.2. Cohesive N-Grams

To show an alternative way of extracting **FL**, I generate top- k n -grams based on association scores. This involves performing statistical calculations that can order the n -grams in a manner that is different from just comparing their frequencies of joint occurrences. For this task, I use a simple probabilistic score based on the Jaccard coefficient [299, p. 49], which captures how much more likely n -grams are to appear together in the n -gram than on their own [300, p. 56]. More specifically, I normalize the joint probability of an n -gram by the sum of the individual probabilities of its constituent words minus the joint probability. The denominator here is different from the original because it represents the sum of the probabilities of the individual words in the n -gram rather than the number of times either word is found. Since this method is primarily used to showcase differences between results of plain and score-based n -grams with regard to functional utility, I am not necessarily interested in counts or scores, but mostly in the resulting top ranks. Therefore, it is necessary to include a minimum frequency threshold for n -grams, given that no limitation can lead to unique yet non-meaningful candidates.

As a concrete example, I highlight 3-grams in Table 4.7.

Scored 3-grams	3-grams
do man zalt	oder horent lesen
oder horent lesen	darnach in dem
gottes geburt druzehenhundert	ze sant gallen
wol getun mochten	an disen brief
lesent oder horent	nach in dem
schaffen verchauffen versetzen	allen den die
gottes gnaden abt	dar nach in
cristus geburt druzehenhundert	man zalt von
phunt wiener phenning	do man zalt
geburt druzehenhundert jar	an disem brief

Table 4.7.: Top-10 score-based vs. plain 3-grams. Scored n -grams are based on candidates with a minimum frequency of 100 occurrences.

According to Table 4.7, formulas considerably differ between the two sequence types, even though there is overlap between them (e.g. 'horent lesen', 'do man zalt') as well as within them. It can also be seen that the scored 3-grams contain phraseological units that are functionally more diverse, and not just the result of high frequency. Besides formulas usually found in a charter's *publicatio* ('oder horent lesen', 'lesent oder horent'), they include references to dates ('gottes geburt druzehenhundert', 'christus geburt druzehenhundert', 'geburt druzehenhundert jar') and a reference to currency units ('phunt wiener phenning').

This example shows that including association scores when generating n -grams renders visible formulas that are not just driven by mere frequency. Notably, while they can be practical, scores are no guarantee for sequences to not pose redundancy, overlap, or even irrelevance. The effects of an association measure can be overly strong, given that the respective function prioritizes the combination of uniqueness and regularity over just the latter. As such, their usefulness depends on how well they can be used to explicate meaningful FL sequences from a given corpus.

To anticipate the problem of redundancy on the one hand, and to extend the range of formula detection techniques on the other, I now demonstrate the use of skip-grams.

4.2.1.3. Skip-Grams

Skip-grams allow for finding sequences of significant cohesion with the option to vary within their structure. Instead of the previous score, I use a modified Log-Likelihood Ratio (**LLR**), i.e., Dunning’s G^2 [119]. As such, I explicitly calculate the expected joint frequency of grams under the assumption of independence between words [301], [302], [114], while with the Jaccard-based measure in Subsection 4.2.1.2, I only do so implicitly and less accurately. In general, the literature even favours **LLR** when quantifying word associations in a corpus that comes with many infrequent occurrences. Moreover, Jesse Hoey [303] implies that G^2 can be well-applied to longer and dynamic sequences.

The employed skip-gram algorithm uses a rolling window to iterate over the text, which identifies, assesses, and optionally adds skip-candidates.¹¹⁹ To generate them, I limit my data set to a sample of 10 %, given that computing skip-grams is of greater cost than n -grams. The results in Table 4.8 offer a glimpse into the dynamics of this algorithm.

Formula	Score
disen brief ansehent (lesent) oder horent lesen	234.02
disen brief sehent (lesent) oder horent lesen	229.05
dreuczehen hundert jar (vnd) darnach in dem	212.93
fur mich vnd (fur) alle min erben	207.41
die disen brief ansehent (lesent) oder horent	205.55
hundert jar (vierzig) (jar) vnd darnach in dem	191.34
an disem prief (vnd) (tvn) (chvnt) allen den di	173.82
die disen brief sehent (lesent) oder horent	169.43
do wir ez (mit) (recht) wol getun mochten	162.24
tag (ze) (phingsten) in dem jar do man	160.10

Table 4.8.: Sampled Top-10 Skip-Grams with $n=6$, $k=3$. Rounded to two decimal points.

As can be seen, optional skips of a sequence are here indicated by brackets. Interestingly, these top candidates contain a large amount of maximum allowed skips.¹²⁰ Comparing the result with previously identified sequences, it seems that, by this method as well, the most common formulas are to be located at the charter’s beginning or the end.

After having presented several ways of how to generate formulas based on a given corpus, I advance to use them in a more concrete application that makes use both of the identification as well as the quantification of **FL**.

¹¹⁹Stephanie Evert conceptualizes this notion as distance-based local window [304, p. 68].

¹²⁰While it would pose an interesting research question — especially in the context of formulaic flexibility —, differences in association between skip-levels are not assessed here.

4.2.2. Formulas Across Sections

A use case especially relevant to diplomatics is seen in examining the extent to which formulas adhere to pre-defined structures in charters. As outlined in Subsection 2.1.3, the charter’s form is a central element to their analysis. For this reason, I use plain n -gram measures to calculate to which segments of a charter the k most common formulas of n length adhere. The text is first divided into a pre-defined number of equal-size segments before n -grams are counted and top candidates are found. I demonstrate this using 10 segments and 5-grams, as depicted in Table 4.9

Segment	1	2
1	allen den die disen brief, 951	vnd tun chunt allen den, 390
2	zu der zeit do wir, 113	sehent oder horent lesen daz, 89
3	swie so daz genant ist, 48	des gotzhus ze sant gallen, 33
4	phunt wiener phenning der wir, 41	dem gotzhus ze sant gallen, 27
5	ze haben vnd allen irn, 44	geben swem si wellen an, 43
6	vnd scherm fur alle ansprach, 46	mit recht noch an recht, 43
7	vnd scherm fur alle ansprach, 62	schirm fur alle ansprach als, 57
8	haben in dem lande ze, 98	daz wir haben in dem, 94
9	an disen brief der geben, 111	insigel gehenkt an disen brief, 84
10	jar dar nach in dem, 633	hundert jar darnach in dem, 529

Table 4.9.: Top-2 5-Grams across 10 Segments.

The results in Table 4.9 clearly indicate which (kind of) formulas are most present in each segment. Furthermore, the formula counts shows their distribution: While the inner segments are comparably sparse regarding formulaicity, the first and last exhibit a much larger number of repetitive language — this is true for the second most common formula per segment as well, and so on. For instance, this shows that around 8 % of all charters contain a specific version of a formula in their *publicatio*, and also over 10 % contain a fixed dating formula.¹²¹

Interestingly, while the top-1 and top-2 slots of each segment pose a high similarity, there is relatively little semantic or structural overlap between the segments’ top slots. This is most likely due to the fact that, when calculating distributions across segments, repetitive sequences can not consolidate and amass, given they are bound to a specific location in the text. I surmise that, as a result, sequences that are similar to the top formula in each segment become indiscernible. This means that, although many other

¹²¹Given that formulas vary in their final form, I believe that a clustered representation of respective formula would result in considerably higher percentages.

formulas might exist and be frequent, they remain concealed.

To conclude this section, a variety of techniques to identify and quantify frequent and significant **FL** were explored.¹²² While I demonstrated more sophisticated sequence types, it turns out that plain n -grams can be meaningfully used to generate new insights with regards to research question of diplomatic relevance. Next up, I test and evaluate other methods to make the phenomenon of formulaic flexibility even more tangible.

4.3. Flexibility

4.3.1. Skip Probability

By building upon the previous work with skip-grams, I generate candidates with skips of interest, and order them by the amount of skipped occurrences, along with their non-skipped version. This approach is based on the assumption that both the association scores as well as the relation between skips and non-skips represents a quantification of these formulas. As such, I comprehend skips as communicative options, rendering the underlying sequence flexible. In other words: I am interested in the distribution of (realized) frequent communicative options.¹²³

For demonstrating this approach, I first generate skip-grams ($n=5$, $k=2$) from a sample of 10 %. Then, the selection is limited to sequences with skips; null and single options are disregarded (e.g., skip-pairs that are only realized once vs. never). After counting occurrences of each skip-gram vs. its equivalent without skips, i.e., in the whole data set, I compare their numbers. Results of this are visible in Tables 4.10 and 4.11: 'With Skips' corresponds to realizations without the option, the opposite is 'Without Skips'.

Both tables very clearly show certain tendencies and preferences of **FL**. For instance, Table 4.10 agglomerates variants of a specific formula and quantifies its (dis-)preferred realizations. Based on this selection, one possible prototype appears to be 'fur mich/vns vnd fur alle min/vnser erben'¹²⁴ Another example is seen in Table 4.11 with 'den di

¹²²As can be seen in the notebook, another use case for formulas lies in the exploration of top n -grams distributions over time, more concretely, their distribution across decades. First findings do suggest certain trends across the corpus, such as changes in favoured dating formulas or the presence of most active issuers. Unfortunately, they are significantly constrained by outliers and skewed due to bias in the data, i.e., a strong presence of charters from certain **MHG** regions (e.g., 'ze sant gallen'). For this reason, more research is needed to gain meaningful insights into the temporal flexibility of formulas.

¹²³Notably, while I deem this section to be about skip *probability*, I do not calculate actual statistics.

¹²⁴Approximately corresponding to 'for me/us and for all my/our heirs'.

Formula	With Skips	Without Skips
do man (zalt) von gottes geburt	520	56
vnd tun chunt allen (den) di	420	6
in dem jar do (man) (zalt) von	368	23
fur mich vnd (fur) alle min	320	213
fur mich vnd fur (alle) min	320	79
fur mich (vnd) fur alle min	320	49
fur vns vnd (fur) alle vnser	307	148
fur vns vnd fur (alle) vnser	307	79
fur vns (vnd) fur alle vnser	307	27
mich vnd (fur) alle min erben	298	226
fur mich vnd (fur) (alle) min erben	298	186
mich vnd fur (alle) min erben	298	63
mich (vnd) fur alle min erben	298	48
die disen brief ansehent (lesent) oder	275	157
brief ansehent (lesent) oder horent lesen	255	163

Table 4.10.: Top-15 skip-grams with $n=5$, $k=2$ by (non-)skips. Sorted in descending order by skips.

disen brief sehent lesent oder horent'¹²⁵ By looking at the relation between skips and non-skips, it can be estimated which variants are more likely in the given data set.

This implementation shows that skip-grams are an interesting way to explicate **FL** and to quantify their flexibility. However, the approach does have some flaws. By solely focusing on structure, some results can be misleading. For instance, Table 4.10 suggests that the top formula is 'do man (zalt) von gottes geburt', with a total of over 500 occurrences without the option. However, the realization without the option renders the given sequence linguistically invalid. Based on this view alone, it is not possible to ascertain how this is compensated. More specifically, it is unclear where the verb would be positioned if it was not realized in the given option, the most likely guess being after the formula's termination. As such, for some occurrences, it is impossible to know whether a formula poses flexibility within its structurally visible boundaries or whether a skip signals syntactic dependency to the outside. This means that, for a more holistic description of formulas, additional identification technique would be needed on top of ranking skip-probabilities.

In summary, although skip-probabilities have clear benefits when analyzing **FL**, their usefulness is limited. More specifically, they do not aid in comprehending linguistic

¹²⁵Freely corresponding to 'for those who see, read, or hear this letter'.

Formula	With Skips	Without Skips
in sehent (lesent) oder horent lesen	109	295
hundert jar (vierzig) (jar) vnd darnach in	21	272
insigel an disen brief (ich) der	10	229
brief sehent (lesent) oder horent lesen	55	226
abt (herman) des gotzhus ze sant	32	196
disen brief sehent (lesent) oder horent	70	194
den die in sehent (horent) oder	29	189
die disen brief sehent (lesent) oder	69	184
tag (ze) (phingsten) in dem jar do	8	171
dem (apt) (des) gotzhus ze sant gallen	3	170
di in sehent (lesent) oder horent	34	169
geben wir in disen (gegenburtigen) (offenn) brief	2	161
insigel (mit) (vrtail) offenlich gehenkt an disen	7	157
mit disem brief (daz) fur mich	20	141
gotzhus ze sant gallen (tun) (kunt) vnd	26	135

Table 4.11.: Top-15 skip-grams with $n=5$, $k=2$ by (non-)skips. Sorted in descending order by non-skips.

nuances in certain formulaic settings. While skip-probabilities can measure formulaic flexibility to some degree, they naturally fail to explain how an absence of words is compensated.

4.3.2. String Similarity

An alternative approach to identifying formulaic flexibility is to frame the search as a sequence similarity detection task. This allows for the identification of potential variations in formulas. There are many different measures that can be used depending on the requirements, i.e., based on edits, tokens, or sequences. To showcase their use, I first compute top- k -grams of the charters, then implement a similarity measure to find similar sequences. For this, I employ Jaccard similarity. In this case, it is used to compare the similarity between given n -grams, with the result being the size of the intersection divided by the size of the union of the sets, i.e., sequences that share the most words. This measure has the advantage of being computationally not too expensive, to a large part because it compares words of a fixed size n . Also, it is less prone to differences in individual characters, rendering it especially useful for investigating word-based variation in historical formulas. Running it with $n=6-8$ and a trivial top- $k=3$, some of the formulas and formulaic variations that are suggested by the algorithm are seen in Table

4.12.

Formula	Variation
do man zalt von gottes geburt	do man zalt von christes geburt do man zalt von gots geburt do man zalt von crists geburt
an disen brief der geben ist ze	an disen brief der geben ist an disen brief der geben ist an der disen brief der geben ist ze der
den die disen brief ansehent lesent oder horent	den die disen brief lesent oder horent lesent die disen brief ansehent lesent oder horent lesent allen den die disen brief ansehent oder horent

Table 4.12.: Selected top formulas of $n=6-8$ with top-3 most similar sequences. Sorted in descending order by pre-computed similarity score.

Corresponding to previous findings, the top formulas can again be allocated to specific parts of a charter’s form. The selected formulas pose interesting variations. The first, which belongs to the *datatio*, highlights a slot that is open to referents to the godly, other than ‘gottes’. The second is belonging to the same segment and shows variation in terms of a formula’s prepositions (‘an’, ‘ze’). The third highlights different options for phrasing parts of the *publicatio*.

Although the implementation of this similarity measure is not particularly sophisticated, it still demonstrates the potential of string similarity measures in capturing variations in language. With algorithmic refinement and greater computational power, these methods can help uncovers flexibility of **FL** in charters.

4.3.3. Sequence Prediction

In this final approach, a more distant method is used to quantify formulaic flexibility, which, in total, requires greater computing power and a larger amount of data than the previous methods. As outlined in Section 3.4, two different (large) language models are fine-tuned to **MHG** charter language.¹²⁶ Here, they are used in sequence prediction tasks, i.e., the (iterative) completion or extension of given formulas based on masked tokens in a given environment. Notably, such **MLM** also provide a confidence score for

¹²⁶I refer to them here as basic and advanced model, much owed to the fact that the former is trained in a simpler architecture, on a smaller amount of training runs, and with a smaller batch size. At least theoretically, this should cause the advanced model to perform better in the set tasks.

prediction candidates. I hypothesize that differences between scores of a prediction set can be understood as a measure of formulaic flexibility, given the model has learned about both structural and semantic properties and derivations of the target language during the training process.

First, I ask the model to predict all parts of some top n -gram individually. To showcase how the quality of a language model can influence respective outcomes, I compute the predictions based on both models on the same input. An example is given in Table 4.13, which shall be qualitatively discussed.

Mask	Basic		Advanced	
	Prediction	Score	Prediction	Score
do	do	0.892	do	0.725
man	man	0.967	man	0.999
zalt	ne	0.135	zal	0.201
von	von	0.997	von	0.990
gottes	Christ	0.792	Christi	0.372
geburt	tag	0.559	genade	0.666
druzenhundert	alle	0.419	dru	0.150
jar	jar	0.932	jar	0.799

Table 4.13.: Mask-fill predictions of a top formula’s tokens by basic and advanced model. Scores rounded to three decimal points. Sorted by sequence succession.

The main takeaway from Table 4.13 is that although both models have similar predictions, the advanced model outperforms the basic one by making at least two partially correct predictions that the basic model misses. However, the scores for these predictions are not entirely clear. From this as well as other examples in the respective notebook, it seems that the basic model tends to make more false predictions with high confidence. Overall, the advanced model is more reliable and accurate than the basic one, which pinpoints their main difference. Nonetheless, since the models are not evaluated quantitatively on larger sets except for the validation during training, these findings are mostly qualitative in nature.

To further explore the aspect of flexibility in formulas, I conduct a comparison of a set of predictions for a specific slot. The slot in question is ‘gottes’ in the formula ‘do man zalt von <mask> geburt druzehenhundert jar’, which is a formula commonly found in a charter’s *datatio*. To generate predictions, I ask the model to name its top-10 candidates for the missing word. The top-10 candidates present an interesting

distribution of scores.¹²⁷ For instance, the top-3 predictions ('Christi', 'Kristi', and 'Crist') share over 80 % of the model's confidence. While the three scores are different, they are considered serious and mutually interchangeable candidates. This represents an instance of formulaic flexibility in one of the most frequent formulas of **MHG** charters, and it highlights the value of **LM** in identifying such instances.

Another interesting and illustrative use case for sequence prediction with **LM**, which inherently thrives with formulaicity, is found in text imputation. In the context of Medieval charters, the model can assist in identifying sequences that have been intentionally left out of, or removed from, a charter, or are missing due to damage or loss over time. This use case involves receiving candidate suggestions for missing text in charters. To achieve this, I consult a list of potential candidates prepared during the pre-processing steps, as described in the dedicated notebook.¹²⁸ I select charters that are written in **MHG**, are transmitted as originals, are scanned, and contain a transcription, making them valid candidates for imputation. By utilizing this approach, it is possible to infer hints on the text that is missing and assess which predictions are likely to be correct.

For this reason, three damaged charters of varying difficulty are chosen, where difficulty is determined by the severity of the damage and hence the amount of text that is likely missing. Predictions are prepared by replacing the missing portions with a pre-defined number of masked tokens.

As per the notebook, the joint forces of both models are likely correct in predicting a person's name for the first candidate's missing text.¹²⁹ As such, depending on whether I propose two or three missing words, the models suggest that one of the missing witnesses is either called Ott, Rudolf, or Heinrich.¹³⁰ The latter candidate is the most likely. This likeliness is given since the last missing word appears to have a trailing 'h', as suggested in the scan — not the transcription. For the second charter, the sequence prediction is already quite difficult, given that the models have to predict two or more consecutive words.¹³¹ In this example, the basic model does not predict meaningful sequences, whereas the advanced model is relatively confident in predicting at least one of the words as 'gehabt' — had. Even though it is impossible to validate this, grammatically I would not deem this unlikely. For the last candidate, I suppose that

¹²⁷It is worth noting that the relative scores of predictions can be influenced by the number of predictions the model's pipeline is configured for. This was taken into account when predicting candidates.

¹²⁸<https://github.com/atzenhofer/ma-thesis-dh-code/blob/master/py/0c-preprocessing-norm.ipynb>.

¹²⁹https://www.monasterium.net/mom/AT-OOeLA/GarstenOSB/1291_VI_09/charter.

¹³⁰Notably, several Heinrichs are present in this charter, which quite possibly stirs the model into a certain direction.

¹³¹https://www.monasterium.net/mom/AT-StiASei/SeitenstettenOSB/1357_V_30/charter.

around 15 words are missing across the whole text.¹³² It is worth stressing here that the joint transcription is obtained by first utilizing the advanced model’s prediction as the primary preference to fill the missing slots. If the advanced model’s prediction is not null, the basic model’s prediction is used as a secondary preference. The result is the following charter transcription:

Ich Wernhart von Weiden vergich offen¹³³ <,> <da> <z> <ich> <mit>
meinem prvder Dietmaren vnd auch allen leuten <,> <da> <ich> <mit>
gvtem willen vnd mit verdoctem mut hon ze <chauffe> <gegeben> andert
halbz viertail weins rethes perkreths, daz <da> <leit> ze Pratheszen, vm
siebenz phenninge vnd avch er <da> <mit> schaffen schol ebichleichen
allen sein frum, daz ich in noch niem <anders> daran schol irrn noch enmag.
Dez gib ich im ze einem worn vrchvnd disen prieff. Daz ist geschehen, do
man zalt von Cristez gepurd drewzehen hundert Jar darnoch in dem zwai
vnd viertzistem iar, des nasten svntages noch phingsten.

Quite surprisingly, the ensemble of models appears to be capable of inserting linguistically meaningful and contextually convincing text that even contains (parts of) sequences that can be described as formulas (‘da ich mit gvtem willen’). As per the notebook, the mean prediction confidence score of the advanced model is considerably higher than in the basic model. Also, the advanced model implements punctuation, whereas the basic model rather includes white space. Another striking point in this example is that the model — which has only learned the structural repetition of **MHG** charters — also appears to take into account (correct) word order depending to the given syntactical environment, i.e., subordinate clauses (’, daz ich’, ’, da ich’). While I simply cannot verify the models’ additions, their predictive power and intuition sheds light on its potential to understand linguistic structure and its dynamics. As such, I do see potential in this to further aid the study of **FL** and its flexibility in charters and beyond.

¹³²https://www.monasterium.net/mom/AT-StiAScho/SchottenOSB/1342_V_26/charter.

¹³³Here, the basic model correctly suggests ‘ich’ as an addition to ‘offen’.

5. Conclusion

Having provided a wide theoretical overview of perspectives on formulaicity in Chapter 2, and having conducted an exploratory analysis thereof in Chapter 4, I now summarize the findings by answering the remaining questions, and thus conclude this thesis.

The first set of questions aimed to assess the degree of **FL** in charters, which is important for situating all other findings. To address **RQ2(a)**, "How formulaic are charters compared to other texts?", several measures were employed, including **LD**, compression, and coverage. Each measure focuses on a different aspect of **FL**, and by calculating and comparing the respective measures across text categories, it was established that the level of **FL** in charters is only moderate. The results show that their vocabulary is relatively diverse, their compression is average, and their structure as per category-coverage varies considerably. Although charters tend to have more repetition within a single instance of them, they are less formulaic than previously assumed.¹³⁴

To address **RQ2(b)**, "Has formulaicity in charters changed over time, and if so, how?", I investigated the development of **FL** measures across the 14th century. The analysis revealed a slight trend towards decreasing formulaicity over time, with Dugast's index and GZIP showing more explicit trends of decreasing formulaicity, while **MTLD** was more ambiguous. This observation is definitive, given that I accounted for the most influential factors that could have skewed the results. While it was ascertained and visually supported how these measures have developed, there is no quick explanation as to why formulaicity in charters has seen this trend.

Aside from tackling **RQ2**, this analysis has shown that **FL** in charters and beyond is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that requires a careful selection and handling of respective measures. I stress that variation in quality of the underlying data can significantly influence the outcome and interpretation of respective results. This highlights the responsibility that lies in pre-processing the data. Therefore, one must be extra cau-

¹³⁴With reference to Subsection 2.2.1, charters can definitely be described as their own text type based on their marked differences from other categories across these measures.

tious when dealing with any form of standardization, normalization, or simplification in historical languages.¹³⁵ This is the case in my analysis as well, since the content of both my corpora¹³⁶ have already undergone some changes and normalization procedures in their transmission history¹³⁷.

By advancing to the next set of questions, the focus is now laid on identifying and quantifying formulas. As such, **RQ3(a)** asks: "What are the most frequent or significant formulas across charters?". To answer it, I employed various techniques to identify most-common and statistically significant sequences, such as by plain n -grams, scored n -grams¹³⁸, and skip-grams. It was found that each form has advantages and disadvantages in representing a charter's typical formula. While some algorithms resulted in clearly conventionalized and functional sequences, a considerable part of the results contained structural and semantic redundancy.

Notably, when it comes to identifying top sequences of any criteria, it is important to consider that this can be a somewhat problematic endeavor. The question of what makes a formula significant or important can be highly subjective, and searching for most common formulas does not necessarily take into account other parameters by which a formula can be identified or deemed meaningful, as described in Subsection **2.2.3**. Therefore, it is difficult to provide a single meaningful answer to this question. Instead, as hopefully demonstrated, a purposeful approach is to compare different techniques for identifying formulas and use them to investigate other aspects of formulaicity.

Exactly for this reason, I recycle generators of said sequence types for tackling **RQ3(b)**, "How are formulas distributed across different sections of charters?". Using plain n -grams, it could be demonstrated that there are overwhelmingly clear tendencies for

¹³⁵In fact, assuming a standardized **MHG** is highly controversial in German Studies. Florian Kragl [305, pp. 4, 19] shares Hermann Paul's opinion from over a hundred years ago that our assumed form of **MHG** tends to be more of a "philological fiction than historical fact" ever since the pioneer work of Karl Lachmann [306]. See also [307] on this and [308] on the problematic relation between modern and **MHG** German.

¹³⁶Regarding the **ReM**, Thomas Klein and Stefanie Dipper write that with this corpus, they intend to record as many linguistically relevant features as possible. However, not all texts are obtained in their original, and some only from 19th century editions, which are far less reliant to capture their origin [283, p. 7]. This results in a stacking of normalization procedures, further complicating the work with historical language.

¹³⁷Over 150 years ago, Georg Waitz remarked (self-)critically on the role which the editor plays in passing down charters. He asks similar questions as I do: How bad do we need originals [309, pp. 440-441]? Should we care that much about character capitalization [309, p. 442]? Should we correct typos in order to increase readability [309, pp. 443]?

¹³⁸I shall point out here that tweaking the association scores resulted in (semi-)Latin formulas emerging from the data. Future research could quantitatively analyze (mutual) influences between Latin and German by building upon pioneering diplomatic work, [179, pp. 196-197], [310], [311], [57], [169].

certain types of formulas to appear in specific segments of the documents. Most significantly, it can be concluded that especially the beginning with the *publicatio* and the end of a charter with the *datatio* pose a high degree of formulaicity with regards to the density of formulas in conjunction with their high frequency. While these results are already quite convincing, it should be noted that only a portion of the formulas could be visibly assigned to specific segments. Due to the nature of how plain n -grams agglomerate, a significant amount of formulas will have remained concealed. To address this limitation, future research could employ algorithms that enable the summarization of formulas into prototypes to allocate them to sequences in a more comprehensive manner. In conclusion, it was demonstrated that computational methods can be used to semi-automatically generate formulas, allocate them to text segments, and identify similar sequences as well.

Narrowing down on formulaic flexibility, the last set of questions asks (RQ4(a)) "How can similar formulas be identified and quantified?", and (RQ4(b)) "To what extent can formulaic language be predicted?". Regarding the former, the identification and quantification of similar formulas can be achieved through various approaches. As demonstrated in Section 4.3, skip-grams can be used to calculate skip-probabilities, whose tendencies to join slots or to alternate can be understood as formulaic flexibility. However, this approach has its constraints, as it fails to address the intricacies of language in specific formulaic contexts or elucidate the manner in which missing words are compensated. To gain a deeper insight into formulas, it would be essential to employ additional identification methods. As a result, a string similarity measure was tested to identify sequences and quantify their distances. Notably, while its results were quite interesting, especially in the face of a low-resource language, I strongly recommend applying more sophisticated string similarity measures to enhance the understanding of FL and its adaptability across contexts and environments.

To answer RQ4(b), I demonstrated use cases of two fine-tuned LMs for sequence prediction. Results show that LMs can accurately complete formulas and provide valuable insights into formulaic flexibility. However, the complex nature of large LMs can make it difficult to fully understand their inner workings and evaluate their results, as highlighted in Subsection 4.3.3. While the employed models were successful in predicting certain sequences and quantifying the flexibility of the micro-environment, understanding why they were able to do so remains a challenge. Nonetheless, these models provide valuable resources for researching FL and its use in historical texts.

Looking back, the benefits of linguistic and computational methods for processing charter language and informing diplomatics have been clearly demonstrated. Also, a plethora of future applications in the field have been outlined. Now, it is key to foster interdisciplinary collaboration for the advancement of knowledge in this area, ultimately benefiting all disciplines involved.

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